

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Country Dossier

Jordan's Governance of Syrian Refugee Returns: Policies and Challenges

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List of Abbreviations

ACF	Action Against Hunger
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
MSF	Doctors without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières)
EU	European Union
GCR	Global Compact on Refugees
ICT	Information and Computer Technology
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
IMC	International Medical Corps
INGOs	International Non-Governmental Organization
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IRC	International Rescue Committee
ISIS	Islamic State of Iraq and Syria
JRP	Jordan Response Plan
MoFAE	Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates
MoI	Ministry of Interior
MoL	Ministry of Labor
MoPIC	Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NRC	Norwegian Refugee Council
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SRAD	Syrian Refugee Affairs Directorate
TCNs	Third Country National
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
WFP	World Food Programme

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The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The project aims to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policy-making”. To this end, GAPs:

- Examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- Analyses enablers and barriers to international cooperation and;
- Explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its de-centring approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyze governance fissures;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU MSs and third countries hinder cooperation on return and;
- A trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary project (2023–2026) coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bicc with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. The 12 countries in which fieldwork has been conducted are Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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Summary

The dossier provides a detailed analysis of the factors influencing Syrian refugee returns from Jordan to Syria. While several areas of Syria, such as Damascus, Homs, and Southern Syria, have seen improvements in security, other regions continue to experience instability. There are some barriers to return: like the sustained security hazards, destroyed infrastructure, dearth of job opportunities, and persecution risk in Syria developed as formidable deterrents against returning by the refugees. Most of them have been detained, extorted, or their property is confiscated upon return. This contributes to the complex decisions made by refugees regarding their return.

Many refugees in Jordan face high living costs, limited job opportunities, and competition for resources, leading to a desire to return home. Despite efforts to issue working permits, many live below poverty, with low wages and job insecurity. Jordan bears a significant resource strain, with job, educational, and public service competition causing tensions in social relationships. Reduced international aid has further increased difficulties for Syrian refugees.

Jordan is implementing return governance and return policies in collaboration with international organizations like the UNHCR. According to all international and local experts interviewed, the scale of return of Syrian refugees from Jordan to Syria remains modest, primarily occurring at an individual level rather than collective or group returns. Jordan's initiatives are about making return safer and providing essential services to help refugees reintegrate into their home country, with the hope of reducing refugee numbers in Jordan and helping Syria's recovery after the war. While Jordan officially presents the return of Syrian refugees as a voluntary process, the reality for many refugees is far more complex. Economic hardships, legal restrictions, may make "spontaneous returns" seem like the only option for many Syrians.

Jordan's approach has been more prudent, offering options like visitor permits, reintegration support, and assistance for temporary returns, but these policies haven't created strong incentives to lead to large-scale return. While Jordan's governance of refugee return has involved navigating complex diplomatic and security considerations, it remains heavily dependent on the willingness of donors to fund the stabilization of Syria and create conditions for return. Similarly, Jordan's role as a regional actor in coordinating refugee return has been a balancing act, managing the diverse interests of Syria, neighboring host countries, and international donors.

1. Introduction

Since the Syrian civil war began in 2011, Jordan has become a major host for around 1.3 million Syrian refugees, with 671,000 registered with the UNHCR.¹ The diverse refugee population includes families, single individuals, and unaccompanied minors. Legal status varies, with many facing challenges related to residency permits and work rights. Syrian refugees face economic, healthcare, education, and social integration issues, including poverty, healthcare access, overcrowding, and resource scarcity.² The Jordanian government has imposed restrictions on refugees. The return of Syrian refugees has been a political issue since the 2011 Syrian civil war. Factors include war dynamics, regional stability, international relations, humanitarian concerns, and domestic politics.³ Countries hosting large numbers of refugees, such as Lebanon, Jordan, and Turkey, have pushed for their return to alleviate economic and social pressures. International organizations have advocated for refugees' safe return, while domestic politics have influenced the agenda. The return of Syrian refugees is a complex issue involving humanitarian concerns, regional politics, and ongoing challenges in Syria.⁴

Some reports indicate that refugees who have returned to Syria, including those from Lebanon, Turkey, and Jordan, have faced arrests. The reasons for these arrests are not specified, but the challenges faced by returnees are highlighted.⁵ The primary actors responsible for the arrests of returnees are the Syrian government and its security forces, including various intelligence agencies. These agencies often target returnees under broad accusations of “terrorism” or disloyalty for having fled the country.^{6,7 & 8}

Returnees are frequently detained without judicial warrants, often at checkpoints or during raids. These detentions can lead to enforced disappearances, with detainees being held incommunicado.⁹ Reports

¹ Abu Al-Hanaa, M. (2024, August 6). *History of Asylum and Displacement in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan*. Centre for Refugee, Displaced Persons and Forced Migration Studies. Available at: <https://rdfmcs.yu.edu.jo/index.php/2022-10-12-06-31-17/3986-2024-08-06-08-28-54> (Accessed 27 February 2025).

² Francis, A. (2015, September 21). *Jordan's refugee crisis*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. <https://carnegieendowment.org/2015/09/21/jordan-s-refugee-crisis-pub-61338> (Accessed 27 February 2025).

³ Ibid.

⁴ Aslim, Z and Abu Mahfouz, H. (2024, December 26). *From Lebanon, Turkey, and Jordan: Regulations for the return of Syrian refugees to their country*. Al Jazeera. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.net/politics/2024/9> (Accessed 26 February 2025)

⁵ Amnesty International. (2021). *Syria: Former refugees tortured, raped, disappeared after returning home*. Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2021/09/syria-former-refugees-tortured-raped-disappeared-after-returning-home/> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁶ Human Rights Watch. (2021, October 20). “Our lives are like death”: Syrian refugee returns from Lebanon and Jordan. Human Rights Watch. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2021/10/20/our-lives-are-death/syrian-refugee-returns-lebanon-and-jordan> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁷ Syrian Network for Human Rights. (2022, December 2). *At least 196 arbitrary arrests/detentions documented in Syria in November 2022, including 11 children and three women, mostly at the hands of Syrian regime forces*. Syrian Network for Human Rights. Available at: <https://snhr.org/blog/2022/12/02/at-least-196-arbitrary-arrests-detentions-documented-in-syria-in-november-2022-including-11-children-and-three-women-mostly-at-the-hands-of-syrian-regime-forces/> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁸ France 24. (2021, September 7). *Syrian refugees tortured, raped, and missing after returning home, Amnesty says*. France 24. Available at: <https://www.france24.com/en/middle-east/20210907-syrian-refugees-tortured-raped-and-missing-after-returning-home-amnesty-says> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

⁹ Syrian Network for Human Rights. (2023, January 3). *At least 2,221 arbitrary arrests/detentions documented in Syria in 2022, including 148 children and 457 women (adult female), with 213 cases documented in December*. Syrian Network for Human Rights. Available at: <https://snhr.org/blog/2023/01/03/at-least-2221-arbitrary-arrests-detentions-documented-in-syria-in-2022-including-148-children-and-457-women-adult-female-with-213-cases-documented-in-december/> (Accessed 22 September 2024).

indicate that returnees are subjected to torture and other forms of ill-treatment during detention. This includes physical abuse, psychological torture, and sexual violence¹⁰ Returnees often face extortion, with security forces demanding bribes for their release or to avoid further harassment.¹¹ Some returnees have their property confiscated or are denied access to their homes and belongings.¹² These factors highlight the severe risks and challenges faced by Syrian refugees who attempt to return to their homeland, despite the ongoing conflict and instability.¹³

The return of Syrian refugees to their homeland is seen as unlikely in the near future, even as the conflict in Syria persists. The economic and security situation in Syria is considered unstable, hindering a safe and sustainable return.¹⁴ The current situation of protracted displacement of Syrian refugees is that the return of Syrian refugees to their homeland remains minimal at this time. Despite some areas in Syria experiencing improved security conditions, the overall economic and security situation is still unstable, making a safe and sustainable return challenging.¹⁵ The Syrian economy has been severely damaged by the prolonged conflict. Essential services and infrastructure are in disrepair, and the economic situation continues to deteriorate. High unemployment rates, inflation, and a lack of basic services such as healthcare and education further complicate the prospects for return.¹⁶ While some regions have seen a reduction in conflict, many areas remain unsafe due to ongoing violence and instability. The presence of various armed groups and the risk of renewed conflict deter many refugees from returning. The war has significantly damaged the Syrian economy, and reconstruction efforts are expected to face substantial hurdles. Reconstruction in Syria faces substantial hurdles. Efforts to rebuild are hampered by limited resources, political complexities, and the need to address widespread destruction. International support is crucial, but the scale of the damage and the ongoing instability make reconstruction a long-term challenge.¹⁷ & ¹⁸ These factors collectively contribute to the protracted

¹⁰ United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner. (2024, February). Syrian returnees subjected to gross human rights violations and abuses – UN report. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2024/02/syrian-returnees-subjected-gross-human-rights-violations-and-abuses-un> (Accessed 23 September 2024).

¹¹ Ibid (Accessed 23 September 2024).

¹² ibid

¹³ ibid

¹⁴ World Bank. (2019). *The mobility of displaced Syrians: An economic and social analysis*. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/syria/publication/the-mobility-of-displaced-syrians-an-economic-and-social-analysis> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

¹⁵ AP News. (2023, May 3). Migrants and refugees in Syria and Lebanon: Safe zones and returns. AP News. Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/migrants-refugees-syria-eu-lebanon-safe-zones-returns-3b52a8b2d55acb6838c1e34916638f4b> (Accessed 21 August 2024). AP News. (2023, April 15). Lebanon and Syria: Refugee returns and challenges. AP News. Available at:

<https://apnews.com/article/lebanon-syria-refugees-returns-ff41047896c7e16d0e5af0fae70d6c31> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

¹⁶ UNHCR. (2022, March 15). Eleven years on, mounting challenges push many displaced Syrians to the brink. UNHCR. Available at :

<https://www.unhcr.org/news/briefing-notes/eleven-years-mounting-challenges-push-many-displaced-syrians-brink>. United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2021). *Syria situation: Global report 2021*. Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/syria-situation-global-report-2021> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

¹⁷ International Rescue Committee IRC. (2023, April 15). Syrian refugees highlight worsening living conditions in the region, and fewer than 2% envisage returning home. International Rescue Committee. Available at: <https://www.rescue.org/press-release/syrian-refugees-highlight-worsening-living-conditions-region-and-fewer-2-envisage> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

¹⁸ Dhingra. (2023, May 2). Syrian refugees face a grim future without international policy shifts. Brookings Institution. Available at: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/syrian-refugees-face-a-grim-future-without-international-policy-shifts/> (Accessed 23 September 2024).

displacement of Syrian refugees, with many finding it difficult to envision a safe and sustainable return in the near future.

Work Package 4 (WP4) of the GAPs project specifically focuses on several critical areas of return migration dynamics and governance:

- 1. South-to-South Return Dynamics and Diaspora Components:** WP4 studies the return migration dynamics within the ‘South-to-South’ paradigm. This includes an in-depth analysis of the role of diaspora communities in influencing and shaping return migration trends and policies.
- 2. Theoretical Approaches and Disciplinary Divisions:** WP4 engages with critical and reflexive theoretical approaches to address and remedy theoretical exceptionalisms and disciplinary divisions that exist between research conducted in the Global North and South. This involves integrating perspectives and methodologies that transcend traditional boundaries and offer a more holistic understanding of return migration.
- 3. Gender Mainstreaming in Programming and Assessments:** WP4, in conjunction with WP3, investigates how implementing actors incorporate gender mainstreaming into their programming and assessments. This ensures that gender considerations are integral to the analysis and development of return migration policies.
- 4. Mapping Dynamics and Governance in Non-European Countries:** GAPs will map the dynamics and governance of return migration in non-European countries to understand the interactions between return migration governance in the Global South and North. The findings from these studies will be compiled into country dossiers, with the most significant outcomes transformed into policy briefs to inform policymakers and stakeholders.
- 5. EU’s Governance and External Dimension:** WP4 broadens the understanding of the EU’s governance of return migration, focusing particularly on its external dimension. It zooms in on the governance of returns in the EU’s neighboring regions, particularly in the Middle East and Africa.
- 6. Drivers of Return and Readmission Policies:** By examining the governance of return migration, WP4 seeks to identify the drivers behind return and readmission policies. A holistic evaluation of legal and policy frameworks (WP2), implementation processes (WP3), and the relations and outcomes for transit and origin countries (WP4, WP7, WP8) will provide evidence of the facilitators and impediments within these policies.
- 7. International Cooperation and Migration Diplomacy:** As the second research dimension, GAPs will focus on the political, societal, and economic issues in transit and origin countries across three return routes. WP4, in coordination with WP2 and WP3, will analyze the interactions among these regions. A specific focus on migration diplomacy (WP5) will offer first-hand data on the obstacles to readmission in countries of origin or transit, suggesting potential avenues for enhanced international cooperation.

The dossier from WP4 of the GAPs project examines return migration governance, gender perspectives, and contextual comparisons. It provides insights into the experiences of return migrants, challenges faced, and specific needs of different gender groups. The report also offers practical recommendations for developing inclusive policies. Key questions include the

effectiveness of governance frameworks, gender dynamics, lessons learned, and best practices for enhancing policies.

2. Methods

With a special emphasis on the Jordanian context with regard to Syrian refugees, the data collection strategy included several techniques to guarantee solid and multifaceted insights. By examining a wide range of sources—including the UNHCR reports *Global Trends: Forced Displacement in 2022*, *Jordan Response Plan for the Syria Crisis (2023–2025)*, and *World Migration Report 2022*, as well as academic articles, policy briefs, and reports from international organizations—we were able to build a solid theoretical and empirical base. This phase helped identify key themes, trends, and gaps in the current understanding of return migration governance. It also provided a contextual background against which further primary data could be analyzed.

The study conducted 15 semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders in Jordan's return migration governance. The interviews included UNHCR representatives, government officials, NGOs, academics, and community leaders. The insights provided insights into governance structures, operational challenges, refugee perspectives, and best practices. The study aimed to understand governance structures, identify operational challenges, capture refugee perspectives, and share successful strategies for improving the effectiveness of return migration initiatives.

3. Context

3.1. Initial Drivers of Outmigration from Jordan to Syria

The initial reasons for Syrians' mass exodus to Jordan were primarily due to the outbreak of the Syrian Civil War in 2011, which led to violence, human rights violations, economic instability, and infrastructure destruction. Jordan provided stability and established refugee camps, making it a viable option for those seeking refuge. The Syrian Civil War led to a significant influx of Syrian refugees into Jordan, with around 1.4 million seeking refuge by 2013. Many received temporary protection and access to services, including healthcare and education. The return of Syrian refugees has been a complex issue, influenced by voluntary returns, safety concerns, reintegration challenges, and political factors. Jordan and international agencies continue to advocate for support to facilitate safe returns and rebuild communities in Syria, but challenges remain significant.

Improved Security Conditions in Syria

One of the primary drivers for Syrian refugees considering returning to their homeland is the improvement in security conditions in certain regions of Syria. As the Syrian conflict has de-escalated in various parts of the country, areas that were previously unsafe have become more stable, making it feasible for refugees to consider returning. According to the United Nations and various humanitarian organizations, several areas have seen a reduction in conflict and increased stability. Table 1 and Figure 2 illustrates that.

- **Damascus and Surrounding Areas:** Since 2018, the Syrian government has regained control over Damascus and its suburbs, leading to improved security conditions. The reduction in active conflict has made it safer for some refugees to consider returning.¹⁹
- **Homs:** The city of Homs and its surrounding areas have also seen a significant decrease in hostilities since 2018. The government's control over these regions has contributed to a more stable environment.²⁰
- **Southern Syria:** Areas such as Daraa and Quneitra have experienced relative calm since the government regained control in 2018. However, sporadic violence still occurs, and the security situation can be unpredictable.²¹
- **Aleppo:** Parts of Aleppo have seen improved security conditions since 2016, particularly in areas under government control. However, the situation remains complex, with ongoing risks in some parts of the city.²²

¹⁹ BBC News. (2018, May 22). Middle East's share of world arms market 'rising'. BBC News, Available at : <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-44198304> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

²⁰ United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2024, February 2). *Syrian Arab Republic: 2024 Humanitarian Needs Overview*. Available at: <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/syrian-arab-republic-2024-humanitarian-needs-overview-February-2024> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

²¹ UK Home Office. (2022, June). *Country Policy and Information Note: Security Situation, Syria*. Available at : <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/syria-country-policy-and-information-notes/country-policy-and-information-note-security-situation-syria-june-2022-accessible> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

²² United Nations. (2024, June 25). 'Syria facing highest levels of humanitarian need since start of 13-year crisis', senior official tells Security Council. Available at : <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15744.doc.htm> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

Table 1: Number of Work Permits Issued to Syrian Refugees in Jordan (2016-2022)

Year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2016-2021	1 st quarter 2022
Total Work Permits	36,790	46,717	45,649	47,766	38,756	62,195	277,873	22,681
Men	35,676 (97%)	44,345 (96%)	43,591 (55.5%)	44,986 (94.2%)	36,117 (93.2%)	56,693 (91.2%)	261,408 (94.1%)	18,690
Women (% total)	1,114 (3%)	2,372 (5%)	2,058 (4.5%)	2,780 (5.8%)	2,639 (6.8%)	5,502 (8.8%)	16,465 (5.9%)	3,911
Flexible Work Permits (% total)	119,692 (until 2021, only health insurance (no social security)) (66.9%)					36,723 (59%)	156,415 (56.3%)	5,698

Source: Al Hussieni, J. (2022). Towards durable and inclusive social protection policies for Syrian refugees in Jordan. Civil Society Knowledge Centre. Available at: <https://civilsociety-centre.org/paper/towards-durable-and-inclusive-social-protection-policies-syrian-refugees-jordan> (Accessed 22 August 2024).

Figure 1: Economic Inclusion of Syrian Refugees Jordan

Source: ReliefWeb. (2023, January). Jordan: Economic inclusion of Syrian refugees. ReliefWeb. Available at: <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/jordan-economic-inclusion-syrian-refugees-january-2023> (Accessed 23 September 2024).

Figure 2: Employment among Syrian Refugees in Jordan

Source: Al Ghurair Foundation for Education. (2021). *Employment trends, challenges, and opportunities for refugees in Jordan*. Al Ghurair Foundation. Available at: https://www.alghurairfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Employment-trends-challenges-and-opportunities-for-refugees-in-Jordan_3.pdf (Accessed 20 August 2024).

The conditions in Syria vary across regions due to ongoing conflict, governance, and humanitarian access. Northwest Syria, including Idlib, is a hotspot for violence and humanitarian crises, with primarily non-state actors controlling the area. Northeast Syria, mainly Kurdish-controlled, faces security tensions and potential threats from Turkish military operations. Central Syria, including Homs and Hama, has limited reconstruction efforts and inadequate infrastructure for returnees. Southern Syria, particularly Dara'a, has experienced renewed violence and unrest, with returnees facing challenges due to security concerns and lack of trust. Damascus and surrounding areas are under tight government control.

Figure 3: Push and Pull Factors Influencing Return of Syrian Refugees from Jordan to Syria

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors.

Policies implemented by host countries and international bodies also play a critical role. Initiatives by the Syrian government to incentivize returns, combined with resettlement and repatriation programs supported by international organizations like the UNHCR, influence the decision-making process of refugees. Additionally, any changes in Jordan's refugee policies, such as reduced aid or stricter regulations, can drive refugees to consider returning to Syria^{23, 24 & 25}.

The European Union (EU) significantly influences Jordan's aid landscape, especially in the Syrian refugee crisis. EU aid supports Jordan through financial assistance and humanitarian aid, providing essential services and boosting the local economy. It also encourages safe and voluntary returns for refugees, enhancing governance capacities and providing incentives for returns. EU aid also promotes stability and security by addressing humanitarian needs and ensuring safe returns. It also includes mechanisms for monitoring returns and influencing Jordan's return policies. EU aid is sometimes conditioned on Jordan's cooperation with EU migration policies, such as bilateral agreements or migration control. This highlights the EU's influence on Jordan's policies on asylum seekers and refugees.

Figure 4: Reasons Why Syrian Refugees Return to Syria

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors. UNHCR (2023). Syria situation.

Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/situations/syria-situation> (Accessed 22 Aug2024).

²³ UNHCR (2022). Syria regional refugee response: Durable solutions. UNHCR. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/100851> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

²⁴ Doosje, B. et al. (2022). Mental health and psychosocial support for Syrian refugees in Jordan: A qualitative study. *BMC Psychology*, 10 (1), 63. Available at:

<https://bmcpyschology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40359-022-00963-w> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

²⁵ Yalim ,Asli Cennet and Isok Kim(2018) Mental Health and Psychosocial Needs of Syrian Refugees: A Literature Review and Future Directions *ADVANCES IN SOCIAL WORK*, Spring 2018, 18(3) Available at: <https://advancesinsocialwork.indianapolis.iu.edu/index.php/advancesinsocialwork/article/download/21633/22052/34713>(Accessed 21 August 2024);

3.2. Arrival and Reception in Jordan

The arrival and reception of Syrian refugees in Jordan have been influenced by a combination of humanitarian response, government policy, and local community dynamics²⁶. The influx began in 2011, following the Syrian Civil War, with Jordan becoming a primary host country²⁷. The initial waves were mostly women and children, seeking stability and safety²⁸. The Jordanian government established refugee camps, providing shelter, food, healthcare, and basic services²⁹. However, many refugees settled in urban areas, causing mixed experiences³⁰. The economic strain on Jordan, competition for jobs, healthcare, and educational resources, and limited legal status have further complicated the situation³¹. International support has been provided to improve living conditions, education, and health services³².

The study, conducted by UNHCR in cooperation with NAMA Strategic Intelligence Solutions, found that 94 per cent of Jordanians have a favorable view on refugees and many feel empathy towards them and their plight. More than 90% of respondents gave the Jordanian government high marks on how they were handling the refugee question. Yet 87% of those polled still believe there are too many refugees in the country and 83% think Jordan has already done more than it should to assist. The survey also indicated that 73% of Jordanians are open to directly helping refugees. Yet 92% report being adversely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite these challenges, UNHCR remains steadfast in its support of Jordan and refugees³³.

The dwindling aid to Jordan, particularly from the European Union (EU), has significant implications for the country's governance and ability to manage return migration, particularly of Syrian refugees. The EU's shift towards internal migration issues and border control has resulted in reduced financial support for countries like Jordan,³⁴ which are on the front lines of the refugee crisis. This has strained Jordan's ability to deliver essential services and maintain social stability, exacerbating tensions and potentially leading to social unrest. The government may need to adapt its policies, seeking alternative funding sources, fostering regional partnerships, or enhancing local governance mechanisms to better manage the integration of returnees within limited means.

²⁶ Awamleh, Z. (2024). Hosting Syrian Refugees through the Development Lens: The Case of Jordan. OpenEdition journals. Available at : <https://journals.openedition.org/remi/25462> .(Accessed 3 November 2024).

²⁷ Alqaralleh, A. (2022, May). Jordan and Syrian humanitarian refugees' dilemma: international law perspective. Science direct. Available at : <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S240584402200665X> .(Accessed 3 November 2024).

²⁸ Francis, A. (2015 September 21). Jordan's Refugee Crisis. Carnegie Endowment for international peace. Available at : <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2015/09/jordans-refugee-crisis?lang=en> .(Accessed 3 November 2024).

²⁹ UNHCR (2022 January) . Jordan: Zaatari Refugee Camp. Available at : <https://www.unhcr.org/jo/wp-content/uploads/sites/60/2022/02/1-Zaatari-Fact-Sheet-January-2022-final.pdf> (Accessed 3 November 2024) .

³⁰ Care(2013 April). Syrian refugees in urban Jordan. Available at : <https://www.care.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/EMER-JOR-2013-Syrian-Refugees-in-Urban-Jordan.pdf> (Accessed 3 November 2024).

³¹ The World Bank in Jordan (2024 February 5). Available at : <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/jordan/overview> .(Accessed 3 November 2024).

³² Ibid

³³ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2020, December 16). Overwhelming majority of Jordanians continue to empathize with refugees. Available at : <https://www.unhcr.org/jo/14355-overwhelming-majority-of-jordanians-continue-to-empathize-with-refugees.html> (Accessed 18 February 2025).

³⁴ Muiderman, Karlijn. (2015 November 26) . The Migration Trail – European migration policies in a globalizing world. The broker news. Available at : <https://www.thebrokeronline.eu/article/the-migration-trail-d94/> .(Accessed 3 November 2024).

Table 2: Number of Syrian refugees in Jordan (2013-2024)

Year	Number of refugees	Refugees in camps	Refugees in non-camps	Male	female	Male in camps	Female in non-camps
2013	579,297	127,796	451,501	----	----	----	----
2018	672,075	126,064	546,011	49.6%	50.4%	----	----
2024	624,499	127,937	496,562	49.7%	50.3%	49.6%	50.4%

Source: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (Aug 31, 2024). Syria regional refugee response: Jordan. UNHCR. Retrieved August 31, 2024. Available at : <https://data.unhcr.org/en/country/jor> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

The data reported for numbers of Syrian refugees registered with the UNHCR was used as the best proxy data source for the number of Asylum Applications, because no Syrians are denied refugee/ asylum status by the Government of Jordan (to date)³⁵.

Table 3: Number of Syrian Asylum Applications (2015-2023)

Year	# of Asylum Applications ³⁶
2015	41,012
2016	53,602
2017	28,667
2018	27,527
2019	22,281
2020	13,271
2021	23,130
2022	17,286
2023	15,058
2024 (until 18 February 2024)	1,776

Source: UNHCR, Data Portal 2024. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/106772> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

³⁵ Turner, L. (2023 November 23) “Who Is a Refugee in Jordan? Hierarchies and Exclusions in the Refugee Recognition Regime, *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 36(4): 877–896, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/feado83> (Accessed 18 February 2025).

³⁶ The number of Syrian refugees and asylum seekers admitted into Jordan and registered with the UNHCR.

3.3. Social, Economic and Political Conditions Led to Development of Return Migration Governance in Jordan

The development of return migration governance in Jordan, particularly for returning Syrian refugees, has been influenced by a combination of social, economic, and political conditions and incidents. As starting point Jordan hosts a significant number of Syrian refugees, which has led to challenges in providing adequate services and maintaining social cohesion as mentioned earlier. Overcrowding in refugee camps and pressure on public services have heightened the need to manage and facilitate returns³⁷.

The prolonged presence of refugees has affected host community-refugee relations, sometimes causing tensions due to competition for resources and employment opportunities. Ensuring peaceful coexistence and integration has been a priority³⁸.

The influx of refugees has placed a considerable strain on Jordan's economy, impacting labor markets, housing, education, healthcare, and public infrastructure. Jordan has lost confidence in international donor support, and faces persistently underfunded humanitarian appeals. Without additional assistance and a sustained response to the refugee crisis, Jordan will continue to limit the scope of protection for Syrians³⁹. Doing so will increase the risk of long-term instability in Jordan. and the region⁴⁰. Diminishing international support has pressured Jordan to develop sustainable strategies for managing the refugee situation, including return migration.⁴¹

Jordan's strategies for managing Syrian refugees and the EU's external migration policies are crucial in understanding the dynamics of return migration governance⁴². As international funding and support have fluctuated due to the ongoing Syrian conflict, Jordan has implemented sustainable strategies to manage the refugee population and prepare for potential return migration⁴³. These include local integration, improving access to education and healthcare, and assessing conditions for safe and voluntary returns. The EU's external migration policy aims to manage migration flows, enhance border security, and support countries affected by migration crises, including Jordan. As aid diminishes, Jordan may seek alternative funding sources,

³⁷ Istaiteyeh, R. (2023). *Charting the path home: Syrian refugee return from Jordan to Syria*. Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/charting-the-path-home-syrian-refugee-return-from-jordan-to-syria> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

³⁸ United Nations Volunteers. (2018). *Facilitating social cohesion between Syrian refugees and host communities in Jordan*. Available at: <https://www.unv.org/Success-stories/facilitating-social-cohesion-between-syrian-refugees-and-host-communities-jordan> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

³⁹ ISWG (2024) . Refugee Response & Resilience Strategy 2024 –2025. Available at: <https://jordanrefugeeshub.unhcr.org/DOCs/ISWG%20Jordan%20Refugee%20Response%202024-25%20Strategy.pdf> .(Accessed 3 November 2024).

⁴⁰ Francis, A. (2015, September 21). *Jordan's Refugee Crisis*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Available at: <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2015/09/jordans-refugee-crisis?lang=en> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

⁴¹ Chehayeb, K. (2022, May 9). Donors pledge \$6.4 billion for Syria at Brussels conference. Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/brussels-syria-donors-conference-bdbf13a6e6aaeb81b53274cb89ddac26> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁴² European Commission. (2022). *Annual Report on Migration and Asylum*. Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-07/00_eu_arm2022_report.pdf (Accessed 3 November 2024).

⁴³ World Bank. (2021). *Jordan Economic Monitor*. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/jordan/publication/jordan-economic-monitor-fall-2021> (Accessed 3 November 2024).

complicating its governance of refugee return⁴⁴. The EU's return policies, which advocate for voluntary and safe returns, have implications for Jordan, which may align its return policies with EU frameworks to enhance cooperation and secure funding⁴⁵.

Jordan has made significant diplomatic efforts to restore ties with Syria, including hosting meetings with Syrian officials to discuss border security, counter-terrorism, and refugee return. Jordan has also emphasized the need for security along its border with Syria, establishing monitoring mechanisms and communication channels⁴⁶. Jordan collaborates with international organizations like the UNHCR and IOM to assess conditions for safe returns, and has implemented humanitarian assistance programs to improve conditions in refugee camps and urban areas⁴⁷. Jordan also participates in regional conferences and engages in bilateral and multilateral dialogues to secure political and financial backing for its refugee management strategies⁴⁸.

Jordan has also negotiated with the Syrian government and international organizations to facilitate the return of refugees. Agreements and understandings on safe, voluntary, and dignified returns have been crucial in shaping return migration governance.⁴⁹ The evolving security and political landscape in Syria, including ceasefires and reconstruction efforts, have influenced Jordan's policies. Improved conditions in Syria are seen as an opportunity to encourage voluntary returns⁵⁰. The statement about the evolving security and political landscape in Syria influencing Jordan's policies relates to how changes in Syria's internal conditions impact Jordan's approach to managing the refugee situation.

Following the mass displacement of Syrians after 2012, Jordan implemented selective border regulations, citing security concerns as the primary justification. The Jordanian state opposed the formal integration of Syrian refugees following their arrival. However, over time, it gradually

⁴⁴ EU Global Strategy. (2020). *A Secure Europe in a Better World*. Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/documents-publications/publications/european-security-strategy-secure-europe-better-world/>. (Accessed 3 November 2024).

⁴⁵ Ibid

⁴⁶ Al Jazeera. (2021). Jordan, Syria Hold Talks to Restore Ties Amid Refugee Crisis. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2016/6/23/syrian-refugees-stuck-on-jordan-border-have-nothing>. (Accessed 3 November 2024).

⁴⁷ The Guardian. (2023). "Jordan Pushes for International Aid to Rebuild Syria and Support Refugee. Available at : <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/February/10/pressure-mounts-on-un-to-provide-urgent-support-to-north-western-syria>. (Accessed 3 November 2024).

⁴⁸ The National. (2022). "Jordan-Syria Security Cooperation: A New Phase in Regional Diplomacy." Available at : https://www.3rpsvriacrisis.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/RSO_2024_full_publication.pdf. (Accessed 3 November 2024).

⁴⁹ Marks, J. (2021). By land or by sea: Syrian refugees weigh their futures. Available at: <https://www.refugeesinternational.org/reports-briefs/by-land-or-by-sea-syrian-refugees-weigh-their-futures/> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁵⁰ Debre, I. (2023, August 23). *Jordan's efforts to return Syrian refugees face challenges*. Available at : <https://apnews.com/article/jordan-syria-refugees-civil-war-return-4a87a2f77db9e6099306db7554898062> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

allowed for labor market integration, particularly in response to incentives from the European Union⁵¹, through the Jordan compact.⁵²

Jordan's approach to Syrian refugees, including the Jordan Compact, is preparing for future return governance. This integration can serve as a form of "return governance," facilitating safe and dignified returns. The experience gained by refugees can benefit Syria's reconstruction efforts. As Jordan strengthens its economic resilience, it can better manage return complexities, including providing support and services for returning refugees. This lays the groundwork for future governance strategies.

Jordan's policies are adjusted based on the security and political developments in Syria. As conditions improve, Jordan sees an opportunity to promote voluntary returns such as: UNHCR Initiatives, Jordanian Government Campaigns, Reconstruction Initiatives, Community Engagement Programs and Incentive Programs. aligning its policies with the goal of reducing the refugee burden while ensuring the safety and dignity of returnees.⁵³ The evolving security and political landscape in Syria provides a context for Jordan to shape its policies and diplomatic efforts, aiming to facilitate the voluntary return of refugees as conditions permit. Jordan has faced international pressure to align with global norms and practices concerning refugee protection and return. Balancing its international obligations with national interests has been a critical factor in policy development. The background and decision to reopen the Nassib-Jaber border crossing are rooted in its historical significance as a crucial trade route between Jordan and Syria. The crossing was closed in 2015 after being overrun by Syrian rebels.⁵⁴ This closure significantly impacted regional trade and the economies of both countries. In October 2018, after Syrian government forces, with the support of Russia, regained control of the area, Jordan and Syria agreed to reopen the crossing.⁵⁵ The decision was driven by several factors in terms that the closure had caused substantial economic losses for Jordan, estimated at around US\$20 billion over three years (2015, 2016, 2017).

⁵¹ Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek and Fatma Yilmaz-Elmas (2024): Refugee governance in the Middle East: insights from Turkey, Lebanon and Jordan In : *Research Handbook on Asylum and Refugee Policy*. Jane Freedman and Glenda Santana de Andrade. PP 159–175. Edward Elgar Publishing Limited. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781802204599.00018> <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/book/9781802204599/book-part-9781802204599-18.xml> (Accessed 20 October 2024).

⁵² The Jordan Compact, established in February 2016 during the London Conference hosted by the United Kingdom, Germany, Kuwait, Norway, and the United Nations, unites international humanitarian and development efforts under Jordan's leadership. This agreement integrates humanitarian and development funding through multi-year grants and concessional loans, with commitments of \$700 million in annual grants over three years and concessional loans totaling \$1.9 billion. Additionally, the Compact obligates the EU to ease trade regulations to boost exports from 18 specified economic zones and industrial areas in Jordan, in exchange for meeting employment quotas for Syrian refugees in these businesses. Available at: <https://media.odi.org/documents/12058.pdf> (Accessed 18 February 2025).

⁵³ Tayser, R. (2023, August 27). 2,582 Syrian refugees left Jordan during first 7 months of 2023 — UNHCR. The Jordan Times. Available at: <https://www.jordantimes.com/news/local/2582-syrian-refugees-left-jordan-during-first-7-months-2023-%E2%80%94-unhcr> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁵⁴ Al Jazeera. (2018, October 14). Life returns to the Nasib border crossing between Jordan and Syria. Al Jazeera. Available at:

<https://www.aljazeera.net/news/2018/10/14/%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D9%8A%D8%A7%D8%A9-%D8%AA%D8%B9%D9%88%D8%AF-%D8%A5%D9%84%D9%89-%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%A8%D8%B1-%D9%86%D8%B5%D9%8A%D8%A8-%D8%A8%D9%8A%D9%86-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A3%D8%B1%D8%AF%D9%86> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

⁵⁵ BBC Arabic. (2018, October 24). "اتفاق أردني سوري على إعادة فتح معبر حدودي مهم بين البلدين". Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/arabic/middleeast-45857150> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

Reopening the border was seen as essential to revive trade and economic activity.⁵⁶ The Syrian government's regained control over the border area and the relative stability in the region provided a conducive environment for reopening. Both Jordan and Syria engaged in diplomatic negotiations to ensure the safe and efficient reopening of the crossing. This included agreements on security measures and customs procedures⁵⁷. The reopening of the Nassib-Jaber border crossing had a mixed impact on the return of Syrian refugees: The reopening facilitated the movement of people and goods, making it easier for refugees to travel between Jordan and Syria. This logistical ease encouraged some refugees to consider returning to Syria⁵⁸.

The mixed impact of the Nassib-Jaber crossing's reopening lies in the interplay of these encouraging factors and the persistent barriers. While logistical ease may motivate some refugees to return, significant concerns about safety, infrastructure, and political stability remain major deterrents, leading to a cautious approach among many refugees when considering return. The resumption of trade provided economic opportunities for both countries, potentially improving living conditions in Syria and making return more attractive for some refugees⁵⁹. Despite these improvements, the overall return rate of Syrian refugees remained low.⁶⁰

Table 4: Numbers of Syrians Returning to Syria from Jordan (2015-2024)

Year	2015	2018	2021	2023	2024
Returnees	Close to 4,000	Around 28,000	4500	2,582	3,162

Source: Norwegian Refugee Council. (2015, October 12). Thousands of refugees return to Syria from Jordan. Available at: <https://www.nrc.no/news/2015/october/thousands-of-refugees-return-to-syria-from-jordan/> (Accessed 25 September 2024)

The UNHCR's role in assessing the conditions for return and providing support for returnees has been instrumental. Joint assessments and reports have guided policy decisions and implementation. Initiatives aimed at integrating refugees into Jordanian society, such as work permits and access to education and healthcare⁶¹, have also shaped the context

⁵⁶ Al Jazeera. (2018, October 14). Jordan and Syria agree to reopen Naseeb border crossing. Al Jazeera. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2018/10/14/jordan-and-syria-agree-to-reopen-naseeb-border-crossing> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

⁵⁷ Cornish, C. (2018, October 30). *Jordan and Syria agree to reopen Naseeb border crossing*. Financial Times. Available at:

<https://www.ft.com/content/e580c1a6-d6de-11e8-aa22-36538487e3do> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

⁵⁸ Jusoor. (July, 2018). Nassib border crossing: Impact of its closure and reopening on Syria and the region. Retrieved September 26, 2024, Available at: <https://jusoor.co/en/details/%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%A8%D8%B1-%D9%86%D8%B5%D9%8A%D8%A8-%D8%A3%D8%AB%D8%B1-%D8%A5%D8%BA%D9%84%D8%A7%D9%82%D9%87-%D9%88%D8%A5%D8%B9%D8%A7%D8%AF%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%81%D8%AA%D8%AA%D8%A7%D8%AD%D9%87-%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%89-%D8%B3%D9%88%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D8%B7%D9%82%D8%A9> (Accessed 25 September 2024).

⁵⁹ Ibid

⁶⁰ The New Arab Staff, T NAS (2021, July 29). Jordan to reopen Syria border crossing at full capacity. The New Arab. Available at: <https://www.newarab.com/news/jordan-reopen-syria-border-crossing-full-capacity> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

⁶¹ UNHCR. *Jordan: How the Global Compact on Refugees is turning into action in Jordan*. Retrieved September 24, 2024, Available at: <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/gcr-action/countries/jordan> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

within which return migration governance has developed. Balancing integration and return policies has been a complex task for Jordan. The interplay between integration initiatives and return migration governance in Jordan reflects a complex reality. While integration efforts aim to provide stability and support for refugees, they can also complicate the prospect of return, as many refugees develop ties to their host country. Jordan must continue to navigate these challenges carefully, ensuring that policies are adaptable to the evolving situation in both the host community and Syria.⁶² Jordan has implemented various local integration programs to support Syrian refugees, which have significantly influenced the governance of return migration. Jordan's local integration programs create a multi-faceted influence on return migration governance. By fostering economic, educational, healthcare, and social integration, these initiatives contribute to a more stable refugee population. However, they also lead to increased challenges in managing return policies, as the likelihood of return diminishes when refugees find security and opportunities in Jordan. Policymakers must navigate this intricate landscape, balancing the need for integration with the realities of potential returns as conditions in Syria evolve. Integration Programs for Syrian refugees in Jordan was introduced through the work permits.⁶³ Jordan's policies aimed to balance the integration of refugees into society with the facilitation of their voluntary return. This involves ensuring that refugees have access to essential services and economic opportunities while also creating conditions that make return a viable option. Jordan's diplomatic efforts to secure agreements for safe and voluntary returns are influenced by the evolving security and political landscape in Syria.⁶⁴ These efforts aim to create a framework that supports both integration and return. Jordan's approach to managing Syrian refugees involves a delicate balance between integrating them into society and facilitating their voluntary return^{65& 66}. Jordan's approach to managing Syrian refugees involves a comprehensive framework of initiatives and policies aimed at integration while preparing for voluntary return. While the government actively integrates refugees into society through programs like the Jordan Compact and educational access, it maintains that these efforts are ultimately geared toward facilitating safe returns when conditions in Syria improve. The emphasis on temporary integration reflects a pragmatic response to an ongoing crisis, balancing humanitarian obligations with national interests. This balance is shaped by economic pressures, international aid dynamics, and the evolving situation in Syria. Effective management requires a coordinated approach involving local, national and international stakeholders to ensure that returns are safe, voluntary, and sustainable.

⁶² Gordon, J. (2021). *The impact of the Syrian refugee crisis on Jordan's economy*. *Journal of Migration and Development*, 1(1), 37-52. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43508-021-00019-6> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

⁶³ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (n.d.). Jordan: How the Global Compact on Refugees is turning into action in Jordan. Retrieved September 24, 2024, Available at: <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/gcr-action/countries/jordan> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

⁶⁴ Kassous, S. (2024, April 27). "We have no power or resources": Syrian refugees in Jordan, Lebanon and "safe return". BBC News Arabic. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/arabic/articles/cy918kdg1jjo> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

⁶⁵ Bani Salameh, M. (2024, February 18). *Beyond Borders: Impacts of the Syrian Refugee Crisis on Jordan*. *Intech Open*. Available at: <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/1185399> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

⁶⁶ Kassous, S. (2023, May 27). *Syrian refugees: Why are host countries now focusing on the issue of voluntary return?* BBC News Arabic. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/arabic/65731848> (Accessed 24 September 2024).

Figure 5: The Governance of Syrian Refugees in Jordan Over Time (2011 - 2024)

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors.

Between 2011 and 2024, Jordan's strategy for managing the influx of Syrian migrants has adapted to shifting regional factors. In the initial phases of the Syrian conflict, Jordan permitted the influx of numerous people seeking asylum by opening its borders. The establishment of refugee camps like as Zaatari and Azraq signified the initial stage of Jordan's refugee governance, concentrating predominantly on humanitarian assistance and emergency response, bolstered by substantial help from international organizations as UNHCR, IOM, and NRC. As the refugee situation became prolonged, Jordan adopted a more systematic and policy-oriented strategy. This encompassed the participation of essential governmental bodies such as the Ministry of Interior (MoI), the Ministry

of Planning and International Cooperation (MoPIC), and the Syrian Refugee Affairs Directorate (SRAD). These institutions collaborated to address the enduring presence of refugees in aspects such as legal status, work, education, and healthcare, striving to reconcile refugee requirements with Jordan's economic and social capabilities. By 2024, Jordan's governance model has increasingly emphasized the integration of refugees into the labor market through different programs, including work permits and access to vital services, alongside the management of refugee camps. Current policies emphasize both fostering refugee self-sufficiency and alleviating the strain on Jordan's resources, increasingly depending on foreign assistance and collaborations with NGOs. The primary government and organizational actors involved in managing Syrian refugees in Jordan include UNHCR, NRC, IOM, the Ministry of Interior (MoI), the Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation (MoPIC), the Syrian Refugee Affairs Directorate (SRAD), and the Ministry of External Affairs (MoEx). The Jordanian government, UNHCR, international organizations, NGOs, donor countries, local community organizations, and private sector all play crucial roles in the country's response to the refugee crisis. The Jordanian government oversees refugee registration, legal status, and access to services like education and healthcare. International organizations provide humanitarian assistance, while NGOs implement programs focusing on education, livelihoods, and healthcare. Donor countries and international agencies provide funding and resources, while local community organizations offer localized support. The private sector also supports refugees through employment opportunities and community projects, as illustrated in Figure 5.

4. Findings

4.1 Characteristics of Return Migration Governance from Jordan to Syria

4.1.1. Scale of Retuning Syrian from Jordan

According to all international and local experts interviewed, the scale of return of Syrian refugees from Jordan to Syria remains modest, primarily occurring at an individual level rather than collective or group returns. The return figures published by the UNHCR periodically⁶⁷ confirm this description of the scale of return. However, UNHCR's return data only includes refugees that are registered with it and is only available from the year 2016 onwards. See Table 1 for an overview of the published data. It is important to note that besides the UNHCR, no other entities, including any governmental or nongovernmental entities, publicly publish refugee data in Jordan. The exclusive role of UNHCR as the 'stock-taking and reporting' entity of the numbers of registered refugees entering, residing in, and leaving Jordan was confirmed during the expert interviews.

⁶⁷UNHCR, Data. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria/location/36> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

Table 5: Annual Overview of Syrian Refugee Dynamics: Total Population, Spontaneous Returns, and Asylum Applications in Jordan

Year	Total No. of Registered Syrian Refugees (Date of Data)	Annual Number of Spontaneous Returns	Annual Number of Asylum Applications	Annual % of Returns Compared to Total	% of Returns Compared to Asylum Applications
2016	667,443 (1 June 2016)	7,165	53,602	1.07%	13.37%
2017	669,013 (19 June 2017)	7,913	28,667	1.18%	27.60%
2018	667,307 (24 June 2018)	7,074	27,527	1.06%	25.70%
2019	665,009 (3 June 2019)	29,409	22,281	4.42%	131.99%
2020	658,010 (3 June 2020)	3,466	13,271	0.53%	26.12%
2021	668,941 (30 June 2021)	5,994	23,130	0.90%	25.91%
2022	676,829 (30 June 2022)	4,013	17,286	0.59%	23.22%
2023	659,457 (30 June 2023)	4,383	15,058	0.66%	29.11%
2024	628,135 (30 June 2024)	3,162	6,760	0.50%	46.78%

Since the year 2016, the total number of registered Syrian refugees in Jordan has remained between a ceiling of 672,075 (recorded in 2018) and a lower limit of 628,135 (recorded in 2024). In the same period, and with the exception of the year 2019, the number of recorded returns as a percentage of the total number of registered Syrian refugees present fluctuated between a peak of 1.21% (recorded in 2017) and a floor of 0.52% (recorded in 2020) between the years 2016 and 2023.

The year 2019 had the highest percentage of returns compared to the total number of refugees present that year (4.49%). It is also the only year (since 2016) that had a higher number of returns compared to the number of asylum applications (131.99% more returns). The desk review and primary data collected could not justify the spike in number of returns in 2019. However, this spike coincides with the opening of the Jordan-Syria Jaber-Naseb border cross in October 2018. The Jaber-Naseeb border crossing represents more than just a physical boundary between Jordan and Syria—it is a symbol of post-conflict recovery, regional cooperation, and the intertwining of economic and security interests. Its reopening in 2018 was a significant milestone in the region, signaling a move toward greater stability and engagement, albeit amid ongoing challenges. The crossing remains a key factor in shaping the future of Jordan-Syria relations and the broader

geopolitics of the Levant. It is *likely but uncertain* that these events are correlated. The 2019 spike also precedes the Covid-19 pandemic, which may have indicated an increase in refugee appetite for returning to Syria, that was then curbed by the pandemic and the consequent government-forced lockdowns and border closures. However, this is also unlikely because return numbers did not rise considerably even in 2023, when all pandemic-related closures and health measures were completely loosened by the Government of Jordan. The increase number of returning Syrian refugees in 2019, which was a result of improvement of security conditions in some areas, economic pressure in host countries, and families' desire to return to their homes. In addition, government initiatives have contributed to encouraging the return by providing some essential services.⁶⁸ Jordan's initiatives are about making return safer and providing essential services to help refugees reintegrate into their home country, with the hope of reducing refugee numbers in Jordan and helping Syria's recovery after the war. In Jordan, there is a low baseline rate of return intentions among Syrian refugees, Despite increasing levels of vulnerability in Lebanon and Jordan, the number of spontaneous refugee returns to Syria has not significantly increased.⁶⁹

However, when discussing the accuracy of return numbers, a local expert (KI7) suggested that the actual figures might be even lower than those reported by the UNHCR. This speculation is consistent with observations made by international experts at UNHCR (KI123). In commenting on the return numbers published by UNHCR, the international experts noted that when a Syrian refugee chooses to go to Syria, they are logged by Jordanian authorities at the border. This information is then shared with UNHCR, which cross-references the data with its own database to verify whether the individuals are registered refugees. This process is how UNHCR generates its return numbers. However, the international experts interviewed commented that UNHCR cannot definitively confirm if these individuals actually left Jordan permanently. This uncertainty arises because Syrian refugees registered with UNHCR can apply for a visitor permit from Jordanian authorities, allowing them to visit Syria for between 1-2 months at the discretion of the authorities and then return to Jordan. One of the international experts noted that there is a consistent migration between Jordan and Syria, with individuals moving for business, for family reasons, for property registration, among many other reasons. As a result, it is possible that some registered individuals who visited Syria returned to Jordan but did not report back to UNHCR to reactivate their registration. Consequently, the return numbers shared by UNHCR could be over reported, but there is no way to determine the exact figures with the current monitoring process.

Despite the uncertainty in the exact numbers of returns, most experts interviewed agreed that the overall trend has remained consistent over the past few years. This suggests a steady, albeit limited, interest in returning among Syrian refugees in Jordan. The stable return numbers are likely more the result of push factors in Syria—especially security concerns and economic hardship—than any active effort or effectiveness of Jordan's governance policy to encourage return. Jordan's approach has been more passive, offering options like visitor permits, limited reintegration support, and assistance for temporary returns, but these policies haven't created

⁶⁸ UNCHR (2019 December 31) "UNCHR continues to support refugees in Jordan Through 2019". Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/jo/12449-unhcr-continues-to-support-refugees-in-jordan-throughout-2019.html> .(Accessed 25 September 2024).

⁶⁹ Human Rights Watch. (2021, October 20). "Our lives are like death": Syrian refugee returns from Lebanon and Jordan. Human Rights Watch. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2021/10/20/our-lives-are-death/syrian-refugee-returns-lebanon-and-jordan> (Accessed 23 September 2024).

strong enough incentives to lead to large-scale return. Instead, refugees are caught in a holding pattern where they're not actively pushed to leave, but conditions in Syria remain too unstable to facilitate widespread return. This view is corroborated by the return data published by UNHCR, as summarized in Figure 6 and Table 6.

Figure 6: Annual Number of Spontaneous Returns of Registered Syrian Refugee from Jordan to Syria

The stability in return numbers is the result of interactions between fluctuating governance practices (in Jordan) and the evolving context in Syria, combined with the structural realities of refugees' lives. Jordan's governance policy, in particular, is designed in such a way that it offers flexibility to refugees without pushing them too hard in any one direction, while still ensuring that they can maintain some degree of stability. The resulting equilibrium is one where return rates stay stable—not because of the strength of incentives or push factors, but because of the balance that exists between the options available to refugees and the conditions they face in both Syria and Jordan.

Table 6: Annual Overview of Actual vs. Intended Returns of Syrian Refugees in Jordan

Year	Annual % of Returns Compared to Total No. of Registered Refugees	Annual % of Surveyed Registered Refugees with an Intention to Return to Syria Within the Next 12 Months
2017	1%	8%
2018	1%	6%
2019	4%	5%
2020	1%	8%
2021	1%	3%

2022	1%	2%
2023	1%	1%
2024	1%	2%

Source: UNHCR- Data Portal. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/109624> (Accessed 18 August 2024).

Social Networks and Community Influence

The influence of social networks and communities cannot be underestimated. Information and experiences shared by early returnees can impact the decisions of others. Positive reports from those who have successfully resettled in Syria encourage more refugees to make the return journey. The initial drivers for Syrian refugees to return from Jordan to Syria are multifaceted, involving improved security conditions, economic challenges in Jordan, better access to services in Syria, emotional and psychological motivations, and policy influences. These factors collectively shape the complex landscape of return migration for Syrian refugees

4.1.2 Types of Return from Jordan to Syria

Despite increasing levels of vulnerability in Lebanon and Jordan, the number of spontaneous refugee returns to Syria has not significantly increased⁷⁰. Jordan's policy towards Syrian refugees is influenced by humanitarian principles, political considerations, and economic realities, reflecting its generosity as a host nation and the challenges it faces due to the influx.

While Jordan officially presents the return of Syrian refugees as a voluntary process, the reality for many refugees is far more complex. Indirect coercion, in the form of economic hardships, legal restrictions, and subtle pressures from both the government and international partners, may make "spontaneous returns" seem like the only option for many Syrians. Spontaneous returns of Syrian refugees from Jordan are a significant and complex phenomenon. While refugees may return irregularly due to a variety of motivations, such as economic hardship or perceived improvements in security, their return is often not systematically monitored. The loss of refugee status typically occurs when a return is voluntary, and there are challenges in tracking these returns, particularly those that take place through irregular channels. Despite this, international bodies like UNHCR, Jordanian authorities, and Syrian actors do monitor the process to varying degrees, although the data on spontaneous returns remains incomplete and unreliable due to the clandestine nature of many of these movements. Although not overtly coercive, these pressures shape the context in which refugees make decisions about returning to Syria, suggesting that their choices may not always be as voluntary as they appear. Jordan's official discourse and policy toward Syrian refugees have shifted from initial humanitarian openness to a more strategic framing that underscores the burden refugees place on the country's resources and security. The "rent-seeking" approach offers a useful lens to understand how Jordan has leveraged the refugee crisis to gain economic support and political benefits, while also addressing domestic concerns.

⁷⁰ Human Rights Watch. (2021, October 20). "Our lives are like death": Syrian refugee returns from Lebanon and Jordan. Human Rights Watch. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2021/10/20/our-lives-are-death/syrian-refugee-returns-lebanon-and-jordan> (Accessed 23 September 2024).

In essence, Jordan has turned its role as a host country into a platform for securing international resources, albeit with the costs of domestic discontent and growing tensions regarding the integration and treatment of refugees.

Box 1: Vignette: The Ongoing Reality of Deportations from Jordan to Syria: A Case of Collective Expulsions and Individual Deportations

Background

In 2017, Human Rights Watch (HRW) reported that around 2,000 Syrian refugees were deported from Jordan back to Syria. These deportations were carried out through collective expulsions and individual deportations, with national security concerns cited as the primary justification. The individuals affected were said to be deemed a threat to Jordan's security. While the HRW article provided the only available empirical data, the actual scale of these deportations has remained hard to verify. This is due to the lack of independent reporting and limited transparency from Jordanian authorities, which is common in the governance of refugee movements. Expert interviews confirmed the occurrence of these deportations, but the exact numbers remain elusive.⁷¹

What stands out, however, is not just the uncertainty of deportation figures but the governance context surrounding the lack of clear information. The silence of Jordanian authorities and the scarcity of official sources is as telling as the deportations themselves, offering insight into the political and operational context that governs refugee policy in Jordan.

The Governance of Deportations:

In 2017, the reported deportations were framed within the context of national security concerns, with refugees suspected of links to militant groups or considered to pose a security threat. However, as reported by HRW and experts in interviews (KI123 and KI6), these expulsions have continued in subsequent years, but the number of deportations appears to have stabilized, often going unreported or not widely discussed by the Jordanian government.⁷²

An important observation is that official reports on deportations from Jordan remain scarce, with little transparency on the process and rationale behind such actions. This lack of information doesn't necessarily speak to the reliability of reports like HRW's but rather highlights governance practices. Experts suggest that secrecy and quick deportation processes - where refugees are detained and deported in less than 24 hours - are a deliberate governance strategy to avoid scrutiny. The absence of detailed figures and the silence of official sources may reflect a strategy of political expediency in managing refugee populations, which includes limiting external oversight and concealing the full scale of expulsions⁷³.

⁷¹ Human rights watch (2017). "I have no idea why they sent us back". Available at : <https://www.hrw.org/report/2017/10/02/i-have-no-idea-why-they-sent-us-back/jordanian-deportations-and-expulsions-syrian> . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁷² Jordan's Refugee Policy and Deportation Laws. Refugee Law and Policy: Jordan. Available at : <https://maint.loc.gov/law/help/refugee-law/jordan.php> (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁷³ IOM Jordan 2021." JORDAN COUNTRY TRENDS REPORT". Available at : https://jordan.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1991/files/documents/jo_country-trends_o.pdf . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

The 2017 Deportations: Collective Expulsions and Individual Cases

According to HRW's 2017 report, the Jordanian authorities executed collective expulsions (groups of refugees deported in a single operation) and individual deportations (single cases of individuals deported back to Syria). The figures cited by HRW indicated that around 2,000 refugees were affected. While HRW attributed the expulsions to national security concerns, including fears of militant infiltration or involvement in Syria's civil war, experts note that such deportations often lack due process, with refugees detained without proper legal recourse⁷⁴.

In interviews with key informants (KI123 and KI16), it became clear that deportations, when they occur, are often handled swiftly and with minimal public disclosure. According to KI6, "When it does happen, it's a quick process — the refugee is detained for 24 hours or less and then deported back to Syria." This expedited deportation process is likely a reflection of Jordan's desire to quickly resolve issues of undocumented refugees or those perceived as threats, without engaging in the complicated and lengthy legal procedures that could attract both international scrutiny and domestic backlash.

Governance and Secrecy:

While the number of deportations in 2017 was substantial, the fact that these figures have not been consistently reported in the years following suggests that the governance of refugee management in Jordan is deeply rooted in secrecy. This is especially evident when compared to the voluntary return processes, which are often conducted through internationally coordinated programs with extensive documentation and oversight by agencies like the UNHCR.⁷⁵

The deportations appear to operate in a parallel system, shielded from the same levels of accountability. This raises important questions: why is there such a gap in transparency? Is it because Jordan wants to avoid international condemnation? Or perhaps, as some experts suggest, it reflects tensions within Jordan's domestic politics, where there is a delicate balancing act between hosting large numbers of refugees and managing national security concerns without appearing to capitulate to external pressures⁷⁶.

Voices from Human Rights Organizations:

To understand the broader context of these deportations and the ongoing challenges, we spoke with Sarah Johnson, a regional advocacy coordinator at Human Rights Watch who has closely monitored refugee issues in Jordan.

Sarah Johnson emphasized that the scarcity of sources on deportations could be more indicative of Jordan's approach to governance rather than a reflection of the accuracy of HRW's report. "The deportations we reported in 2017, and that continue to happen today, reflect a broader pattern of governance in Jordan," she said. "In a highly sensitive political environment, especially with

⁷⁴ Human Rights Watch (2017). "I have no idea why they sent us back". Available at : <https://www.hrw.org/report/2017/10/02/i-have-no-idea-why-they-sent-us-back/jordanian-deportations-and-expulsions-syrian> . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁷⁵ UNCHR (2024). Operational data portal. Available at : <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria/location/36> . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁷⁶ Jordan's Refugee Policy and Deportation Laws. Refugee Law and Policy: Jordan. Available at : <https://maint.loc.gov/law/help/refugee-law/jordan.php> . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

regard to Syrian refugees, deportations are often executed swiftly, with little legal oversight, and most importantly, minimal external visibility. The lack of independent sources comes from the fact that Jordan is determined to manage these expulsions under the radar”⁷⁷.

According to Johnson, the governance of return and deportation in Jordan operates under a system of opacity, where limited transparency is often the preferred strategy. “This doesn’t just affect the number of deportations we can track. It’s about the very structure of refugee management in Jordan. When deportations happen, they often occur without legal process or clear communication to either the refugees or to the public. This is by design. Jordan is a country under constant pressure from both the international community and its own citizens, who are increasingly frustrated with the refugee presence.”⁷⁸

Implications for Refugees

For refugees caught in this system, the implications are grave. Deportations are often quick and without due process, leaving individuals vulnerable to abuse and unsafe conditions upon return to Syria. As KI123 noted, “There is a fear among refugees that, should they be caught in such a situation, they will not have the time or resources to contest the deportation or even understand why they’re being sent back.”⁷⁹

The swift nature of deportations prevents many from having a fair chance to contest their expulsion, let alone seek legal recourse. This lack of transparency surrounding the deportation process exacerbates refugees’ vulnerability and mistrust toward authorities.

Insights

The deportations of Syrian refugees from Jordan in 2017 and ongoing today reveal complex and opaque governance practices. The lack of transparency and rapid deportation processes is part of a deliberate strategy to limit external scrutiny. This opaque system leaves refugees vulnerable to arbitrary expulsions, highlighting the need for transparency and accountability in managing the refugee crisis.

The UNHCR maintains the same position the Government of Jordan on the return of Syrian refugees to Syria: return must be voluntary, when conditions for a safe, dignified and sustainable return are in place⁸⁰. UNHCR’s role in facilitating voluntary return and preventing forced deportations is critical in the Jordan-Syria refugee context. Through programs like Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR), legal advocacy, monitoring border areas, and engaging in information campaigns, the agency strives to ensure that refugees can return to Syria safely and voluntarily, with the necessary support for reintegration. However, despite these efforts, UNHCR faces

⁷⁷ Human rights watch (2017). “ I have no idea why they sent us back”. Available at : <https://www.hrw.org/report/2017/10/02/i-have-no-idea-why-they-sent-us-back/jordanian-deportations-and-expulsions-syrian> . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁷⁸ Ibid

⁷⁹ UNCHR (2024). Operational data portal. Available at : <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria/location/36> . (Accessed 29 Non 2024).

⁸⁰ UNHCR –Data Portal. Available at: https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria_durable_solutions (Accessed 20 August 2024).

significant challenges: a lack of transparency from governments, political pressures, and the ongoing instability in Syria complicate its efforts. According to some of the interviewed experts (KI123, KI6, KI8), there are currently no governmental or non-governmental actors in Jordan promoting the return of Syrian refugees to Syria. Furthermore, some of the interviewed experts (KI4, KI7) that are in direct contact with Syrian refugees noted the refugees' fears about returning to Syria due to ongoing security concerns and the challenging living conditions. The experts suggested that these fears significantly influenced refugees' decision-making regarding return, noting that many would opt to remain in Jordan despite a desire to return to their homeland. They added that the current situation in Syria, particularly regarding security and stability, plays a significant role in determining the feasibility of return.

Experts predicted that there may be increasing pressure from the Jordanian public to see Syrian refugees return as the economic conditions in Jordan worsen. Nevertheless, there is insufficient information to determine whether and to what extent these shifts in public support for hosting Syrian refugees would influence the Government's position. For instance, over the past two years, the Government has issued public statements confirming its position to continue hosting Syrian refugees and seeking support from the international community to enable this⁸¹, while also making statements that indicate a soft shift in the opposite direction, such as the Jordanian Minister of Interior's statement in February 2024 that Syrian refugees 'will not be resettled in Jordan'⁸², and the Jordanian Minister of Foreign Affairs' call for the establishment of a global fund aimed at supporting the voluntary and safe return of refugees because 'the future of Syrian refugees lies in their homeland'⁸³. On the diplomatic front, during the same time period, Jordan launched the Jordan Initiative which aims to normalize Arab relations with the Syrian government, and with refugee returns being one of the key issues in the Initiative's scope⁸⁴.

4.1.3 Actors in Jordanian Governance of Syrian Return

According to some of the interviewed experts (KI123, KI6, KI8), there are currently no governmental or non-governmental actors in Jordan promoting the return of Syrian refugees to Syria. Nevertheless, figure 7 shows a description of the key actors involved in governing the presence and spontaneous return of Syrian refugees in Jordan.

⁸¹Jordan Times Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/foreign-minister-calls-increased-support-syrian-refugees> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

Jordan Times⁸² Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/syrian-refugees-will-not-be-resettled-jordan-%E2%80%94-interior-minister> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

⁸³Jordan Times. Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/jordan-calls-global-fund-voluntary-safe-return-syrian-refugees> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

⁸⁴Ersan, M. (2023, April 4). Jordan's plan for Syria normalisation: Refugees, drugs and militias. Middle East Eye. Available at : <https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/jordan-syria-plan-normalisation-refugees-drugs-militias> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

Figure 7: Key Governance Actors in Syrian Refugee Returns in Jordan

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors.
MoEX and MoFAE are used interchangeably.

Government of Jordan entities

The Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation (MoPIC) in Jordan coordinates international aid, develops national response strategies, and aligns refugee initiatives with Jordan's development goals. It secures financial support, manages stakeholder relationships, and integrates refugee needs into long-term national planning. MoPIC also monitors aid effectiveness and supports infrastructure projects.

Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates (MoFAE) is a Jordanian organization that advocates for Jordan's interests globally, secures international support, and coordinates with global partners to align refugee assistance with national policies.

Ministry of Interior (MoI): The Jordanian Ministry of Interior (MoI) issues identification documents for refugees, maintains national security, and oversees border control. It works with international organizations like UNHCR and NGOs to coordinate assistance and protection efforts. The MoI also oversees refugee camps, regulates movement, and contributes to policy development and enforcement, balancing national security interests with humanitarian obligations to the refugee population.

Syrian Refugees Affairs Directorate (SRAD): The Syrian Refugee Camp Affairs Department was established in 2013 to manage Syrian refugee affairs within refugee camps. In 2014, it expanded to include all Syrian refugees across the Kingdom. SRAD now oversees and secures refugee camps, implements government policies, and monitors refugee status. It also documents and registers refugees, facilitates transactions, addresses legal violations, and guides international aid projects.

International Organizations

The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) is responsible for managing Syrian refugee affairs in Jordan, providing essential aid, facilitating resettlement, and supporting voluntary returns to Syria. The UNHCR coordinates with the Jordanian government and other organizations to advocate for increased international support. However, it does not promote spontaneous returns to Syria, focusing on border monitoring, information sessions, and monitoring refugee perceptions. The success of voluntary return programs depends on cooperation between Jordanian and Syrian authorities and the international community's support. The UNHCR's role is critical in ensuring due care, accountability, and respect for international protection standards.

Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC): The NRC provides essential humanitarian aid to Syrian refugees in Jordan, including food, shelter, and emergency relief. They focus on education, livelihoods, legal aid, and protection services. The NRC also engages with refugee communities and coordinates with the Jordanian government to enhance support. They facilitate the spontaneous return of Syrian refugees to Syria, providing legal documentation support and counseling. However, their involvement is limited, focusing on neutral humanitarian support and avoiding advocating for refugees' rights and needs.

International Organization for Migration (IOM): The International Organization for Migration (IOM) is crucial in the Third Country Resettlement of Syrian refugees, providing essential aid, ensuring refugee protection, and promoting resilience and capacity building.

Others: Many other international organizations in Jordan have collaborated with the Government of Jordan and other stakeholders to provide humanitarian and reintegration support to Syrian refugees in Jordan since 2013. These include, but are not limited to, the International Rescue Committee (IRC), CARE International, Save the Children, the World Food Programme (WFP), UNICEF, Mercy Corps, Oxfam, Doctors Without Borders (MSF), International Medical Corps (IMC), Relief International, and Action Against Hunger (ACF).

The Syrian Government

The Syrian Constitution and government statements support the right of return for refugees, but implementation is contested due to security, political realities, and fear of persecution, posing significant challenges for the safe, voluntary, and dignified return. The government is also responsible for cooperating with international organizations and host countries to coordinate the return process. However, all of the interviewed experts expressed concerns about the government's commitment to creating genuinely safe conditions, noting that many refugees fear persecution, harassment, or inadequate living conditions upon their return. One expert (KI4)

noted that the Syrian Government called on refugees to return, but this call was widely perceived -both by Syrian refugees and the international community- as a weak attempt to present the situation in Syria as "normal." Approximately two years ago, the Syrian Government introduced a law requiring Syrians to periodically prove land ownership, or risk having the land claimed by the state. Law No. 10 of 2018 has had far-reaching implications for Syrian refugees and their property rights. The law's provision requiring proof of ownership within a set timeframe has led to widespread fears that many refugees will lose their land and property, especially given the challenges of proving ownership from abroad. The law also risks creating further barriers to voluntary return for refugees, as the fear of dispossession is likely to discourage many from coming back to Syria, particularly when the safety and security of their property cannot be guaranteed. The measure was intended to motivate, or indirectly pressure, refugees to return. Nevertheless, the expert concluded that the low number of returnees suggests that these efforts were largely ineffective.

4.1.4 Policies Governing Return on Syrians from Jordan to Syria

According to the Jordan policies between 2011-2024: Jordan's policies in dealing with returnees reflect a delicate balance between the desire to support refugees and the necessity of addressing economic challenges- as shown in Table 7- while committing to ensuring that return is safe and voluntary.^{85&86}

Table 7: Jordan's Initiatives for the Repatriation of Syrian Refugees

Time	Policies to Enforce Return
2011-2016	Between 2011 and 2016, Jordan followed a policy of hosting refugees with limited support for their return.
2021-2017	Between 2017 and 2021, return policies has changed. Jordan continued to support refugees, but it has begun to encourage voluntary return. In response, Jordan worked with UNHCR, Syria, and international donors to facilitate the return process through expedited procedures, return packages, and legal assistance, while also ensuring that returns were safe and voluntary ⁸⁷ . Some facilities were provided, such as expediting return procedures such as : Reopening of the Jordan-Syria Border (2018), Expedited Return Procedures and Streamlining of Processes (2017-2021) Voluntary Return Packages (2017-2021), Legal Assistance for Property Rights (2018), Coordinated Efforts with UNHCR for Reintegration Support (2018-2021),

⁸⁵ Awalmeh.Z. (2024). "Hosting Syrian Refugees through the Development Lens": The Case of Jordan. Open Edition Jordan. Available at: <https://journals.openedition.org/remi/25462> . (Accessed 25 August 2024).

⁸⁶ UNCHR. "Operational data portal. Available at: " <https://data.unhcr.org/en/countries> . (Accessed 25 August 2024).

⁸⁷ The Jordan Times. (2021). "Jordan's refugee burden: A review of the facts. Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/unhcr-reveals-rising-refugee-poverty-amidst-jordans-economic-challenges>. (Accessed 5 November 2024).

Efforts to Promote Security in Return Areas (2018-2021) ,Encouragement of Voluntary Return via Public Messaging and Regional Cooperation (2020-2021) and Economic Incentives for Returnees (2020-2021) ,but the economic situation was affecting the refugees' ability to stay.

2022 In 2022, Jordan continued its policy of supporting Syrian refugees, with a focus on voluntary return. Jordan encouraged voluntary return through facilities for refugees who wish to return to Syria, such as Jordan-Syria Border Reopening Agreement (2018), UNHCR Voluntary Return Program (2017-2021), Property and Documentation Facilitation (2018), Reintegration Assistance Program (2019-2021), Safe Zones Return Incentive Program (2020-2021), Economic Reintegration Program (2020-2021), and Jordan's Voluntary Return Statement (2019-2021).

The difficult economic conditions in Jordan have affected the number of refugees who decided to stay, making return an option for some of them.

Cooperation with international organizations: Jordan has worked with UNHCR, continued to offer voluntary return packages to Syrian refugees. These packages typically included transportation, medical care, temporary housing, and legal assistance.

2023 In 2023, Jordan continued to adopt a policy of voluntary return for Syrian refugees, while enhancing cooperation with international organizations⁸⁸.Some discussions from Jordanian Government: Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates: Led diplomatic discussions with the Syrian government and international stakeholders regarding the voluntary return of refugees.

have taken place with the Syrian government to facilitate returns, but the security situation in certain areas still poses a barrier for many.

2024 In 2024, Jordan continues to adopt a policy of voluntary return for Syrian refugees.

The Jordanian government continues to encourage refugees to return voluntarily, providing some facilities and information about the situation in Syrian areas. The ongoing economic pressures in Jordan have led some refugees to consider returning as an option for a better life. Jordan collaborates with humanitarian organizations to provide support and assistance to returning refugees, emphasizing the necessity for their return to be safe and sustainable.

Source: Salem, Ajluni (2019 March). "The Syrian Refugee Crisis in Jordan and Its Impact on the Jordanian Economy". WANNA institute. Available at:

https://wanainstitute.org/sites/default/files/publications/Publication_Executive%20Summary_English.pdf

(Accessed 23 September 2024).

UNCHR. "Operational data portal " Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/countries>.

Government of Jordan (2016 January 14)" Jordan Response Plan for the Syria Crisis 2016-2018". ReliefWeb.

Available at:<https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/jordan-response-plan-syria-crisis-2016-2018> .(Accessed 23September 2024).

⁸⁸ Jordan's Response to the Syria Crisis: 2023 Update. Available at : <http://www.jrp.gov.jo/> (Accessed 5 November 2024) .

1. Syrian Government Policies and Initiatives

The Syrian government has a number of policies and initiatives aimed at encouraging and managing the return of refugees, though these efforts are complicated by security, political, and economic realities.

a. National Reconciliation and Right of Return

Right of Return: The Syrian constitution guarantees the right of return for all displaced Syrians. The Syrian government asserts that all refugees are free to return to their homes in areas controlled by the government, positioning the return process as part of the broader effort of national reconciliation⁸⁹.

Amnesty Laws: The Syrian government has offered amnesty for individuals who may have been involved in anti-government activities, aiming to ensure that returnees are not prosecuted for their past actions.

b. Law No. 10 (2018)

Property Registration Law (Law No. 10): Introduced in 2018, this law requires Syrian citizens to prove ownership of property within a certain timeframe. Failure to do so allows the government to seize and redistribute property. This law has been criticized for creating significant obstacles to the return of refugees who lack access to their property documents or who fear losing their homes if they are unable to return in time⁹⁰.

c. Security Guarantees and Return Conditions

Security Assurances: The Syrian government claims that regions under its control are now safe for returnees. However, refugees are wary of security threats such as detention, military conscription, and retaliation by government forces or affiliated militias. The return process is thus fraught with fear for many, despite official assurances of safety⁹¹.

2. Jordanian Government Policies and Initiatives

The Jordanian government is an important player in the return process as it has both diplomatic relations with Syria and is a host country to over 1.3 million Syrian refugees. Jordan's policies reflect its economic strain from hosting large numbers of refugees, as well as its security concerns and relations with both Syria and the international community.

a. Diplomatic Engagement with Syria

Reopening of the Jordan-Syria Border (2018): After years of closed borders, Jordan and Syria resumed diplomatic ties in 2018, reopening the border for both trade and refugee returns. This gesture signaled Jordan's support for voluntary returns and its desire to facilitate the recovery of Syrian territory under government control⁹².

⁸⁹ UNCHR (2024), Syrian Refugee Return: Policy and Perspectives. Available at : https://www.3rpsyriacrisis.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Intention_Survey_RPIS_2024.pdf . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁹⁰ Human Rights Watch (2018). Syria: Questions and Answers on New Property Law. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2018/05/29/syria-questions-and-answers-new-property-law> .(Accessed 29November 2024).

⁹¹Human Rights Watch (2024). Syria events in 2023. Available at : <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/syria> .(Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁹² Aljazeera (29 September 2021). Jordan fully reopens main crossing with Syria. Available at:

b. Voluntary Return Programs

UNHCR-Supported Returns: Jordan collaborates with the UNHCR to facilitate voluntary returns for refugees who wish to return to Syria. Jordanian authorities have stated that they are open to facilitating returns, provided that conditions are safe and voluntary, but they also rely on the UNHCR's monitoring to ensure that returnees are not coerced.⁹³

Coordination with Syrian Authorities: Jordan cooperates with Syrian authorities to ensure that returns are coordinated through safe channels, but there is a reliance on Syrian assurances regarding the security of returnees.

c. Economic and Political Pressure

Internal Pressures for Return: Public sentiment within Jordan has consistently pressured the government to facilitate refugee returns due to the economic burden that refugees place on Jordan's limited resources, including access to health care, education, and employment opportunities.

Limited Integration: While Jordan has allowed some refugee integration (e.g., work permits in certain sectors), it remains a temporary solution given the economic constraints and regional security concerns⁹⁴.

3. International Organizations' Policies and Initiatives

International actors, including UNHCR, the EU, and donor countries, have been instrumental in both facilitating returns and ensuring that returns are voluntary, safe, and dignified. These actors also seek to hold the Syrian government accountable for its treatment of returnees and ensure that refugee rights are upheld.

a. UNHCR's Role in Return Facilitation

Voluntary Return Assistance: The UNHCR facilitates voluntary returns through transportation and post-return support in Syria. The UN agency also provides legal support to refugees to ensure their safe return and re-integration. Refugees are provided with information on security conditions, living conditions, and property rights to make an informed decision⁹⁵.

Monitoring Return Processes: The UNHCR monitors refugee returns to ensure that returns are voluntary, and that refugees are not coerced or pressured. They have return monitoring teams that assess the conditions in areas of return to verify that refugees will be safe upon return.

<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/29/jordan-fully-reopens-main-crossing-with-syria> .(Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁹³UNCHR (2023). Syria situation 2023-2024. Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/situations/syria-situation> .(Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁹⁴ World bank group (2024). Jordan: Improving Economic Opportunities for Syrian Refugees and Host Communities. Available at : <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2024/11/06/jordan-improving-economic-opportunities-for-syrian-refugees-and-host-communities> . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

⁹⁵ UNCHR (2024), Syrian Refugee Return: Policy and Perspectives. Available at : https://www.3rpsyriacrisis.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Intention_Survey_RPIS_2024.pdf . (Accessed 29 November 2024).

Awareness Campaigns: The UNHCR conducts information campaigns to inform refugees about the conditions in Syria, including risks of returning to specific areas. This is meant to counter any misinformation or coercion that could push refugees to return against their will.

b. EU and Donor Countries' Conditional Support

Safe and Voluntary Return Conditions: European countries and donors have expressed concerns about the safety of returning to Syria, and their support for return is conditional on guarantees from the Syrian government that returns will be voluntary and safe. EU governments have emphasized the importance of ensuring protection for refugees, particularly those who may face persecution or retribution upon return.⁹⁶

Reconstruction Aid and Pressure: The EU has conditioned financial support for Syria's reconstruction on human rights and the protection of returnees. Some European countries have warned that reconstruction aid will be limited unless there are clear guarantees from the Syrian government regarding the dignity and safety of returning refugees.

c. Conditional Support for Returnees

Incentivizing Voluntary Returns: Some donor countries, particularly those in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), have expressed interest in funding reconstruction efforts in Syria, with the expectation that it will improve the conditions for the safe return of refugees. However, many Western donors, particularly the U.S. and EU, are cautious about contributing to Syria's reconstruction without significant political reforms in the country.

Financial and Logistical Assistance: Donor countries and international organizations provide financial resources to support both refugee accommodation in Jordan and post-return support in Syria. This can include transportation costs, rehabilitation of housing, and livelihood support in certain areas of Syria⁹⁷.

4. Key Initiatives and Mechanisms Supporting Return

Several initiatives are currently in place to support the return of Syrian refugees, ranging from international agreements to local coordination mechanisms:

a. Jordan-Syria Return Agreement

Jordan-Syria Bilateral Agreement: Jordan has signed agreements with Syria to facilitate the return of refugees under specific conditions, including ensuring that returnees are not coerced and that voluntary returns are supported by UNHCR and other international organizations.

b. UNHCR's Return Packages and Support

Return Packages: The UNHCR provides refugees returning to Syria with transportation assistance and temporary accommodation once they arrive. These packages also include access to legal documentation and support for reintegrating into local communities in Syria.

⁹⁶ EEAS (2024). The EU and the crisis in Syria 26. June .2020. Available at : https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/eu-and-crisis-syria-0_en . (Accessed 2 November 2024).

⁹⁷ Middle east eye (2023) Syria's return to the Arab diplomatic fold is not a top concern for Biden. Available at : <https://www.middleeasteye.net/opinion/syria-us-reintegration-arab-diplomatic-fold-biden-concern> . (Accessed 29 November 2024)

c. Syrian Government's "Safe Zones"

"Safe Zone" Initiatives: The Syrian government has established areas within government-controlled zones that are promoted as safe for returnees, especially in regions like Damascus, Homs, and Aleppo. These areas are presented as secure, though they remain under close scrutiny and oversight by Syrian forces, militias, and intelligence agencies.

In contrast to Lebanon's context, where the treatment of Syrian refugees is influenced by unique socio-political dynamics and resource constraints, the Jordanian government's approach to encouraging voluntary return appears to be centered around diplomatic negotiations and regional partnerships⁹⁸. The Jordan's efforts to spearhead negotiations between Arab states and the Syrian regime, aiming to facilitate the repatriation of Syrian refugees. Moreover, the normalization of relations between Arab states and the Assad regime may indirectly contribute to more forceful deportations, as observed in Lebanon's context.⁹⁹

Jordan has been actively involved in diplomatic efforts to encourage the voluntary return of Syrian refugees since the Syrian conflict began in 2011. The country has hosted over 1.3 million refugees, putting significant strain on its resources, infrastructure, and economy. Jordan has played a pivotal role in fostering dialogue between the Syrian regime and other Arab states, including the Gulf countries¹⁰⁰. In 2018, Jordan reopened its border with Syria after years of closure due to the conflict, signaling a shift in relations and the beginning of a more diplomatic approach to Syria¹⁰¹. Jordan has been involved in facilitating the safe return of refugees, working closely with the UNHCR and other international partners. In 2020, Jordan, along with Syria and Lebanon, agreed to a trilateral plan that would encourage the return of refugees¹⁰². The Amman Declaration (2021) highlighted the need for a coordinated approach to the repatriation of Syrian refugees, emphasizing the need for safe, voluntary, and dignified returns while also stressing the need for reconstruction efforts within Syria.¹⁰³

Regional partnerships for refugee return involve a broad coalition of Arab states, including Lebanon, Turkey, Iraq, and other Arab states. Turkey, hosting the largest number of Syrian refugees, has been actively involved in negotiations, particularly through its engagement with Russia and Iran, which are both key allies of the Assad regime.

⁹⁸ Beaujouan, J and Rasheed, A (2022), *The Syrian Refugee Crisis in Jordan And Lebanon: Impact And Implications*. Available at: <https://peacerep.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/MEPOPaper-JBAR-002.pdf> .(Accessed 23 September 2024).

⁹⁹ Heydemann, S (2024, August 2). Syria normalization: The failure of defensive diplomacy. Brookings Institution. Available at: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/syria-normalization-the-failure-of-defensive-diplomacy/> (Accessed 27 August 2024).

¹⁰⁰ Middle East Institute. (2020). "Gulf States and the Future of Syria's Reconstruction. Available at : <https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/policy-analysis/syrias-normalization-and-gcc-adjusting-new-modus-vivendi> (Accessed 5 November 2024).

¹⁰¹ Al Jazeera. (2018). "Jordan reopens border with Syria after years of closure. Available at : <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/29/jordan-fully-reopens-main-crossing-with-syria> .(Accessed 5 November 2024).

¹⁰² UNHCR Jordan. (2020). "Voluntary Return from Jordan to Syria". Available at : <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria/location/36> .(Accessed 5 November 2024)

¹⁰³ The Jordan Times. (2021). "Jordan's refugee burden: A review of the facts. Available at : <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/unhcr-reveals-rising-refugee-poverty-amidst-jordans-economic-challenges> .(Accessed 5 November 2024).

Key diplomatic and practical steps have been taken to facilitate refugee return, such as the UNHCR's involvement, international pledges and assistance, and the creation of safe zones and infrastructure¹⁰⁴. However, significant challenges remain in making the return of refugees both safe and sustainable. Jordan's visitor permit system manages the Syrian refugee crisis, offering flexibility but posing challenges in monitoring, return statistics, and migration patterns. Addressing these requires improved monitoring, clearer guidelines, and stronger regional cooperation, as circular migration complicates refugee management and integration efforts.

5.1.5 Practices on Governing Return of Syrians from Jordan to Syria

One of the interviewed experts (KI6) mentioned that local media occasionally raises the possibility of forced returns of Syrian refugees from Jordan when international aid is reduced or cut. However, the expert emphasized that these discussions have not led to any policy changes, agreements, or public statements from the Jordanian government that would support such claims. The speculative discussions about forced returns of Syrian refugees from Jordan when international aid is cut are directly linked to EU external migration policy, which often involves balancing voluntary returns, burden-sharing, and humanitarian support. While the EU advocates for safe and voluntary returns, the decreasing financial aid and increasing migration pressure could lead to shifts in local policies, which might raise concerns about forced returns. The EU plays a critical role in shaping Jordan's approach to refugee returns, and its future funding decisions, diplomatic engagement with Syria, and pressure on Jordan to facilitate returns will likely continue to influence these debates.

“Every now and then, when international aid is cut or reduced, we do hear mainstream media discuss the possibility of forced return of Syrian refugees from Jordan, but this has never materialized in policy or agreement shifts, or in any public statements from the Government of Jordan that indicate the validity of these predictions. These waves typically die down rapidly on their own.” – KI6

Regardless, the expert notes that in 2024, however, several developments have raised concerns among refugees about whether Jordan might be employing indirect methods to encourage returns.

while Jordan has not explicitly forced refugees to return, the indirect push factors that have raised concerns among refugees in 2024 appear to be the unintended consequences of economic hardship, policy adjustments, and regional pressures. Jordanian authorities may welcome the outcomes of these factors, as they align with both economic needs and international pressure to manage the refugee population. However, it is more likely that these measures are indirect responses to the country's difficult circumstances and broader geopolitical dynamics, rather than

¹⁰⁴ UNHCR (2020). “UNHCR’s Monitoring of Refugee Returns to Syria. Available at : <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria> (Accessed 5 November 2024) .

intentional actions aimed at coercing refugees to return. The key changes reported by the expert k16 are as follows ¹⁰⁵.

1. Jordan increased the monthly subscription fees that employers must pay to the Social Security Department for their Syrian employees, leading to a reduction in employment opportunities. For many Syrian refugee families, these jobs were their primary source of income.
2. There were significant cuts in UNHCR funding in the first quarter of 2024, with additional reductions in April. This decrease in financial aid has impacted the support available to Syrian refugees. Although the Government of Jordan is actively seeking solutions and additional funding, some refugees perceive these cuts as a soft strategy to force their return to Syria.
3. The Government of Jordan imposed a deadline for Syrian refugees living in urban areas to renew their Service Cards with the Ministry of Interior by the end of April 2024. The potential consequences for failing to renew are unclear, leading to speculation within the refugee community that this requirement could be another tactic to encourage returns to Syria.

4.2 Driving Forces of Return Migration Governance from Jordan to Syria

4.2.1. Interests of Return Migration Governance: Domestic, External

The interests of return migration governance: are both domestic and external, since the return of Syrian refugees in Jordan to Syria can be multifaceted. Several potential domestic interests arise, notably economic relief ¹⁰⁶ (i.e., reducing the financial burden on Jordan's economy by decreasing the number of refugees reliant on state resources). An additional domestic interest is in alleviating pressure on public services such as healthcare, education, and housing.

Mitigating social tensions between refugees and host communities ¹⁰⁷ is also an interest. The tensions between refugees and host communities can stem from both objective scarcity issues (real, tangible challenges) and political scapegoating (a more subjective, often manipulated narrative). Both factors contribute to a complex, multi-layered dynamic that can amplify conflict, but they do so in different ways.

¹⁰⁵ UNHCR Jordan Vulnerability Assessment (2023). Available at : <https://data.unhcr.org/en/working-group/54> (Accessed 5 November 2024); Human Rights Watch (2024): "Jordan: No Jobs, No Future: Refugees and Work in Jordan". Available at : <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/jordan> (Accessed 5 November 2024).

¹⁰⁶ UNHCR. (2023). Jordan country operation update: August 2023. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/106139> (Accessed 30 August 2024).

¹⁰⁷ Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. (2015). *Jordan's refugee crisis*. Available at: <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2015/09/jordans-refugee-crisis?lang=en> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

In addition, addressing concerns of local populations (Jordanians) regarding employment and resource allocation. Enhancing political stability by addressing public concerns over the prolonged presence of refugees and reinforcing national identity and social cohesion by managing the refugee population, is also an aim for Jordan reducing¹⁰⁸ potential security risks associated with large refugee populations and ensuring that returning refugees do not pose a security threat to Jordan¹⁰⁹. The security risks associated with large refugee populations—whether related to radicalization, criminal activities, or instability—are significant concerns that heavily influence return governance. These risks drive the formulation of policies focused on screening, monitoring, and reintegration of returnees, as well as the management of public perceptions and regional cooperation. The balance between humanitarian concerns and security risks often dictates the framework within which returnees are allowed to come back, the terms of their reintegration, and the extent of scrutiny they undergo.

One of the interviewed experts (KI7) highlighted the crucial role of Jordan's economic situation in shaping the dynamics of return migration. From the perspective of governance actors, economic conditions—such as unemployment rates, public sector capacity, and the overall stability of the economy—are central to decisions about facilitating or discouraging return. In particular, the Jordanian government's capacity to absorb returnees, provide them with job opportunities, and integrate them into the national labor market is influenced by economic challenges. Governance actors must weigh the potential economic burden of reintegrating returning migrants against the need to stabilize and develop the economy. Moreover, the government's interest in managing return migration may be influenced by external factors, such as international aid or political pressure from donor countries, which may be linked to economic incentives or conditions. Thus, the economic context in Jordan directly shapes the strategies and interventions of state and non-state actors involved in managing return migration. The external interests can be in demonstrating compliance with international agreements and obligations regarding refugee return and strengthening diplomatic ties with donor countries and international organizations that support refugee return initiatives^{110, 111}.

Managing the return of refugees in a way that is safe, dignified, and voluntary requires a multifaceted approach that goes beyond the logistics of physical return. It necessitates comprehensive support for reintegration, economic cooperation, and regional stability. By collaborating with international organizations like the IOM, adhering to international standards such as SDG 10.7, and working toward the reconstruction of Syria, both Jordan and Syria can ensure that the return process contributes to lasting peace and prosperity. Through regional cooperation, cross-border economic initiatives, and international support, both countries can

¹⁰⁸ Karasapan, O. (2022): *Syrian refugees in Jordan: A decade and counting*. Available at : <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/syrian-refugees-in-jordan-a-decade-and-counting/>

¹⁰⁹ Council on Foreign Relations. (2022). *U.S. and international policy to protect refugees: A timeline* Available at: <https://www.cfr.org/blog/us-and-international-policy-protect-refugees-timeline> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

¹¹⁰ International Law and Policy Brief. (2022). *International obligations of asylum countries to protect refugees*. The George Washington University. Available at:

<https://studentbriefs.law.gwu.edu/ilpb/2022/04/29/international-obligations-of-asylum-countries-to-protect-refugees/> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

¹¹¹ International Organization for Migration. (2020). *Assisted voluntary return and reintegration (AVRR): Thematic paper*. Available at: https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1486/files/our_work/ODG/GCM/IOM-Thematic-Paper-Assisted-Voluntary-Return-and-Reintegration.pdf (Accessed 31 August 2024).

achieve the stability and economic growth necessary for a successful and sustainable return of refugees¹¹².

Returning to a secure environment free from conflict and persecution, and ensuring personal and familial safety during and after the return process, is among the factors of interests for Jordan¹¹³. Access to employment opportunities and economic support for sustainable reintegration and securing livelihood opportunities such as healthcare, education, and housing, is required¹¹⁴. Social and cultural reconnection¹¹⁵, through reconnecting with family, community, and cultural ties in Syria and reestablishing a sense of normalcy and belonging in their homeland is a target. The goal is to secure legal status and recognition in Syria and reclaiming property and assets left behind during displacement. These interests highlight the complex interplay between domestic and external factors influencing return migration governance and the multifaceted needs and aspirations of returnees.

Competing interests at different levels make up the political economy of return. By promoting repatriation, host nations like Jordan may experience less economic hardship and more security, but they may also use the presence of refugees as leverage to secure foreign assistance. Countries of origin, especially Syria, want refugees to return in order to support economic restoration and human capital, but they face obstacles related to infrastructure, security, and international pressure. While local communities frequently bear the costs and benefits of refugees' presence or return, international actors strike a balance between humanitarian ideals and political realities. This interaction shapes how return migration is governed and managed, with complicated ramifications for both refugees and the participating nations. Though it was a positive step in 2018 when Syrian refugees in Jordan were given permission to start home-based businesses in certain sectors, very few have so far registered due to the need for a valid passport – which 95% of them do not have¹¹⁶. There are also limitations to starting businesses outside the home, including the need to enter into a joint venture with a Jordanian partner¹¹⁷. Refugees already face high levels of poverty and unemployment. Reduced aid exacerbates these issues, pushing refugees into deeper economic distress. In response to the economic strain, host countries may implement stricter regulations and policies that limit refugees' rights and access to services. These policies can indirectly

¹¹² Obeidat, R. Middle East Institute. (2021). *Border opportunities: Reviving the Jordan-Syria free trade zone*. Available at: <https://www.mei.edu/publications/border-opportunities-reviving-jordan-syria-free-trade-zone> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

¹¹² European External Action Service. (n.d.). *The European Union and Jordan*. Retrieved September 16, 2024, Available at: https://www.eeas.europa.eu/jordan/european-union-and-jordan_en?s=201 (Accessed 31 August 2024).

¹¹³ Frelick, B. Human Rights Watch. (2023, September 29). *No, Syria is still not safe for refugee returns*. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/09/29/no-syria-still-not-safe-refugee-returns> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

¹¹⁴ Culbertson, S. & Kumar, K. Rand Corporation. (2019, March 1). *Jobs can improve the lives of Syrian refugees and their hosts*. Available at: <https://www.rand.org/pubs/commentary/2019/03/jobs-can-improve-the-lives-of-syrian-refugees-and-their.html> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

¹¹⁵ Norwegian Refugee Council. (2019). *Legal identity and housing, land, and property rights of Syrian refugees from a durable solutions perspective*. Available at: <https://www.nrc.no/globalassets/pdf/reports/legal-identity-and-hlp-rights-of-syrian-refugees/legal-identity-and-hlp-rights-of-syrian-refugees-from-a-durable-solutions-perspective---english.pdf> (Accessed 31 August 2024).

¹¹⁶ Buswell, M. (2020, June 29). *How to get Syrian refugees working in Jordan and Lebanon*. World Economic Forum. Available at: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/06/syrian-refugees-jordan-lebanon-employment/> (Accessed 22 September 2024)

¹¹⁷ Ibid

force refugees to consider returning to Syria¹¹⁸. Moreover, reduced support can also lead to increased social tensions between refugees and host communities. This can create an unwelcoming environment, further pressuring refugees to leave. In extreme cases, the lack of international support can lead to forced returns through deportations or coercive measures by host countries. This is often a last resort when host countries can no longer sustain the refugee population. These factors collectively contribute to a situation where Syrian refugees may feel compelled to return to their home country, despite the ongoing risks and instability there.

The push and pull variables that influence Syrian refugees' decisions to stay in Jordan or return to Syria are largely shaped by governance practices in both countries. While the Syrian government's reconstruction efforts and pledges of property reclamation serve as pull forces, Jordan's policies—particularly those pertaining to employment limitations and long-term integration barriers—create powerful push factors. However, the degree to which these variables are controlled by all-encompassing policies that not only attend to the needs of refugees but also offer a safe and stable environment for returns in Syria will determine how effective return migration administration is overall. The effectiveness of return migration governance will ultimately depend on how well humanitarian needs, political stability, and economic recovery are balanced.¹¹⁹

4.2.2 Capacities of Return Migration Governance

In discussing the existing and needed capacities for return migration governance in Jordan, most interviewed experts agreed that while current capacities in Jordan are adequate for small-scale, the capacities needed for effective return migration governance are varied and complex, depending on the roles and responsibilities of the different actors involved. Host governments, countries of origin, international organizations, NGOs, local communities, and the private sector all play distinct yet interconnected roles in facilitating the safe, voluntary, and dignified return of refugees.

These actors must have the necessary institutional, technical, financial, and political capacities to ensure the success of return migration programs. Only through effective coordination, resource mobilization, and targeted reintegration efforts can returnees be successfully reintegrated into their home countries, and regional stability be restored.

voluntary returns, they would be strained by a larger-scale return (KI5, KI6, KI7, KI8). The role of existing INGOs in supporting the Government of Jordan in the governance of return migration was also highlighted as a strength point to be leveraged in Jordan (KI8). One expert (KI6) noted that a currently ongoing discussion within the Government of Jordan and some INGOs is the facilitation of return at a larger collective scale, whereby it is acknowledged by all parties that that would require human, financial, and material resources to operate the 'exit' process efficiently,

¹¹⁸ UNHCR. (2022, March 15). *Eleven years on, mounting challenges push many displaced Syrians to the brink*. UNHCR. Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/news/briefing-notes/eleven-years-mounting-challenges-push-many-displaced-syrians-brink> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

¹¹⁹ United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2023). *Syrian Arab Republic: Humanitarian access severity overview* (June 2023). Available at: <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/syrian-arab-republic/syrian-arab-republic-humanitarian-access-severity-overview-june-2023> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

from providing returning refugees with information, legal assistance and documentation support, closure of their legal situation in Jordan, border controls at both ends, amongst many other considerations. The conversation around facilitating the return of refugees at a larger collective scale in Jordan, as pointed out by KI6, reflects a growing recognition within the government, international organizations, and NGOs of the complex and resource-intensive nature of such a process. Given the ongoing displacement crisis in Jordan and the region, this discussion involves multiple stakeholders, including governmental actors, international donors, humanitarian organizations, and local communities.

“Jordan certainly does not have the human, institutional, or material capacities required to process and manage the sudden return of almost 650,000 Syrian refugees. If the return is very gradual and temporally spread out, that is manageable.” – KI7

A recent example of a donor-funded project that could aid Jordan in managing return migration is the Integrated Border Management in Jordan Project, funded by the EU and implemented by the International Center for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) in partnership with the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). This project, which ran from July 2019 to July 2023, aimed to support Jordan in developing an integrated approach to border management, enhancing its capacity to combat transnational crime, and strengthening trade facilitation practices and measures ¹²⁰. Although no publicly available resources directly link the project to managing the (large-scale) return migration of Syrian refugees, it serves as an example of efforts that could potentially fortify the Jordanian government's ability to handle such returns, should they occur. Jordan's preparedness for large-scale refugee returns is essential because it directly influences the country's political, social, and economic stability, as well as the human rights of refugees and the broader regional security environment. By proactively managing the return process, the Jordanian government is ensuring that it can handle the practical and political challenges of large-scale returns, while maintaining its international standing and contributing to regional peace.

It is not just about managing the logistics of return; it is about mitigating risks, fostering cooperation, and laying the groundwork for long-term stability—in Jordan, in Syria, and throughout the region. The successful preparation and management of this process will ultimately help reduce tensions, avoid forced returns, and provide dignified and voluntary solutions for refugees. On the other hand, an important point raised by some of the interviewed experts was the capacities and role of Syria in governing return migration. It was highlighted that improved diplomatic relations and coordination between Jordan and Syria would be essential should large-scale returns occur (KI5), and that the major deficiencies lie in the capacities within Syria rather than in host countries like Jordan (KI4).

4.2.3 The Role of EU in Return Migration Governance from Jordan to Syria

European Union (EU): The EU remains committed to supporting Syrian refugees in Jordan while advocating for peace and stability in Syria. It promotes the voluntary and safe return of

¹²⁰ ICMPD. Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/integrated-border-management-in-jordan-ibm-jordan> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

refugees and ensures continuous aid in areas such as protection, education, and livelihoods, primarily through funding other national and international organizations in Jordan. Recent EU-funded initiatives include enhancing access to education and vocational training for Syrian refugees, supporting the economic participation for women through targeted skill training and job opportunities, a €60 million program to improve education quality and accessibility, a €43 million program to enhance primary healthcare access and quality for Syrian refugees and vulnerable host community members, and the EU Madad Trust Fund to support the National Social Protection Strategy to create sustainable livelihoods for Syrian refugees. According to the EU¹²¹, Since the beginning of the Syria crisis in 2011, the EU has channeled roughly €3.5 billion to Jordan through humanitarian, development and macro-financial assistance. Of this total, humanitarian aid amounts to over €431 million. In 2024 alone, the EU mobilized €14 million in humanitarian assistance to support health care, education, and protection assistance. Furthermore, in a meeting with the Jordanian Foreign Affairs Minister in June 2024, European Commission Vice President Margaritis Schinas affirmed that the EU and its member states pledged an additional 6 billion euros to support host countries, including Jordan, at the 8th Brussels Conference on Supporting the Future of Syria and the Region ¹²².

The EU's multifaceted initiatives in Jordan clearly aim to address both the immediate needs of refugees and the long-term goal of safe, voluntary, and dignified returns. Through enhancing education, providing livelihoods, supporting health and social protection systems, and investing in Syria's future stability, the EU creates an environment where refugees have the resources and options to make informed decisions about returning. However, by improving the living conditions of refugees and host communities in Jordan, the EU also implicitly delays the return process until conditions in Syria are truly conducive to a safe and sustainable reintegration. Thus, while the EU's actions are not directly designed to enforce or speed up returns, they undoubtedly shape the conditions that will make returns possible in the future.

The international experts interviewed at UNHCR confirmed that the EU plays a major role in many aspects when it comes to Syrian refugees in Jordan, particularly as a key donor to the UNHCR for the refugee assistance and protection programs that it implements in Jordan. On another layer, the EU works with the Government of Jordan in other important development and social protection frameworks. They also noted that the EU also has a key role to play in the context of stabilizing Syria and supporting the countries where return can materialize. This view was shared by another interviewed expert (KI5), who noted that the EU (and other international organizations) should be increasing their efforts to stabilize Syria and improve living conditions and prospects for returning refugees in order to realize the internationally agreed-upon precondition of voluntary, safe and dignified returns.

¹²¹ European Commission –Jordan. Available at: https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/where/middle-east-and-northern-africa/jordan_en#how-are-we-helping (Accessed 20 August 2024).

¹²² JT. (June 05,2024) . *Safadi, EU's Schinas discuss partnerships, refugee support. Jordan Times*. Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/safadi-eus-schinas-discuss-partnerships-refugee-support> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

Another expert (KI4) suggested that the EU played a significant role in shaping the policy ecosystem governing the presence of Syrian refugees in Jordan. According to this expert, the onset of the Syrian crisis led to an ‘understanding’ between Jordan and the EU. This arrangement, namely the Jordan Compact, entailed Jordan ‘absorbing’ a large number of Syrian refugees in exchange for international aid and more relaxed trade regulations with the EU, which would facilitate Jordanian exports to European markets. The expert concluded that the EU supported Jordan in achieving economic benefits “in exchange for taking a hit from the Syrian crisis” and speculated that this understanding was a major factor behind Jordan’s reluctance to enact legislation or policies that would enforce or encourage the return of Syrian refugees.

The EU’s role in the return of refugees from Jordan is deeply tied to aid dynamics, stabilization goals, and the economic agreements between Jordan and the EU. Jordan demands more stabilization in Syria and increased funding for returnees to ensure their reintegration, while the EU responds cautiously, balancing its humanitarian goals with political constraints. The way in which aid is structured—whether it encourages, conditions, or restrains return—directly influences the feasibility and success of return processes, and is a critical factor in shaping the overall governance of return migration.

4.3 Effects of Return Migration Governance from Jordan to Syria

4.3.1 Consequences for Regional Return migration: Protection, mobility, Diplomacy

The Government of Jordan does not force the return of Syrian refugees and asylum seekers to Syria. The official stance is that any return should be entirely spontaneous, and that any return must be safe and no refugees should be returned to areas where they face threats to their safety, security, or human rights. This stance aligns with the protection and non-refoulement principles articulated under Article 7 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which was ratified by Jordan in 1975¹²³. The influence of Jordan’s governance of refugee return to Syria on the legality, mobility, and diplomacy of returns is discussed below.

Influence of Jordan’s governance of refugee return to Syria on the legality of returns:

When discussing the legality of refugee returns to Syria, several interviewed experts agreed that so long as Jordan continues to maintain this stance, and does not force, coerce, or motivate (directly or indirectly) any returns to Syria (in its current security, political, and economic situation), then Jordan remains in good adherence with the protection and non-refoulement principles (KI6, KI7, KI8). Any shifts in this stance or any exercise of ‘soft’ pushes to motivate return without sufficient improvements in the security, political, and economic situation in Syria would raise questions around the legality of these returns and the up keeping of the protection and non-refoulement principles. The deportations and expulsions of Syrian refugees in the

¹²³ UN Treaties. Available at: https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=IV-4&chapter=4&clang=en (Accessed 25 August 2024).

context could indeed raise serious legal concerns regarding non-refoulement, due process, and the right to asylum. If refugees were sent back to Syria in circumstances where conditions remained unsafe, or if their returns were made under coercion rather than voluntary choice, this would violate key international legal principles. The soft push for return in the absence of real improvements in Syria's conditions would put Jordan, the EU, and other involved actors at risk of legal liability, including human rights violations and refoulement claims.

To avoid such legal risks, Jordan and international actors must ensure that all returns are voluntary, safe, and dignified, and that the legal and protection needs of the returnees are met in full accordance with international law. EU and Jordanian policies should focus not only on stabilizing regions of Syria but on ensuring that the basic rights of refugees are upheld at every step of the return process.

Influence of Jordan's governance of refugee return to Syria on the regional mobility of returns:

The regional mobility of returns for Syrian refugees is shaped by a complex set of factors, including economic conditions, security, legal frameworks, and political relationships between Jordan, Syria, and other host countries.

- Re-returns to Jordan are likely when security conditions or economic opportunities in Syria fail to meet returnees' needs.
- Movement to third countries can occur due to family reunification, resettlement opportunities, or the search for better livelihoods and safety.
- Jordan's policies and practices around border management, reintegration support, and regional cooperation can significantly influence the likelihood of re-return or regional migration patterns among Syrian refugees.

Several interviewed experts agreed that the regional mobility of Syrian refugees in Jordan will primarily depend on the situation in Syria and the refugee policies of Jordan and other host countries (KI4, KI6, KI7, KI8). One interviewed expert suggested that if a refugee voluntarily decides to return to Syria, it is likely a calculated decision, indicating they no longer wish to live in Jordan or any other host country - assuming their return was entirely voluntary, without any indirect coercion (KI6). However, other experts noted that if the security, political, and economic conditions in Syria deteriorate or fail to improve, re-migration could be expected (KI4, KI7, KI8). One likely scenario is that returnees who wish to leave Syria again might re-migrate to Jordan, given the life and community they have established there over the past 13 years (KI4). However, if Jordan's stance on hosting returning refugees were to change, re-migration might shift toward neighboring countries with more welcoming policies (KI7).

“If the security, social, economic, and political situation in Syria is stable, then global returns to Syria may be catalyzed by regional returns, because more refugees will want to get reunited with their families in their homeland, and will want to slip back into their old rhythms and forgo the ‘refugee’ label. However, if returns are to an unstable Syria with the current security, social, economic, and political situation - we should expect future waves of re-

migration to Jordan, Turkey, Lebanon, Europe... with no intention to ever return.” - KI7

It is important to note that Jordan's governance of refugee returns will significantly impact regional mobility, particularly if refugees from neighboring host countries decide to return to Syria and then re-migrate to Jordan instead due to policy changes in their original host country regarding refugee return or hosting.

Influence of Jordan’s governance of refugee return to Syria on the diplomacy of returns:

Over the last 12 years, the question of refugee return has significantly influenced Jordan’s relations with donors, regional host states, and Syria. The Jordan Initiative has played a key role in shaping Jordan’s diplomatic engagement with Syria and in positioning itself as a key player in the region's refugee management. While Jordan’s governance of refugee return has involved navigating complex diplomatic and security considerations, it remains heavily dependent on the willingness of donors to fund the stabilization of Syria and create conditions for return. Similarly, Jordan’s role as a regional actor in coordinating refugee return has been a balancing act, managing the diverse interests of Syria, neighboring host countries, and international donors. The aforementioned mobility of Syrian refugees is likely to impact diplomatic relations between Jordan and other host countries in the region, depending on the direction of potential re-migration waves occur because the ‘elephant in the room’ remains unaddressed – that is, the unstable and uninviting situation in Syria. One interviewed expert suggested that this could strain diplomatic relations if Jordan is forced to carry the burden of an additional refugee influx due to policy changes in neighboring host countries that no longer wish to accommodate Syrian refugees (KI8).

“With what is going on in Lebanon, if Syrian refugees are forced to return to Syria right now in its current condition, and with Jordan’s current welcoming stance, what’s to stop these same Syrian refugees from migrating to Jordan? Jordan would then either pay the price for its humanitarian hospitality by having to bear the weight of an additional refugee influx, or it will be coerced into changing its political stance and refusing entry at its borders, or even forcing the return of the refugees it currently hosts.” – KI8

Influence of Jordan’s governance of refugee return to Syria on the interregional mobility of returns:

Several interviewed experts suggested that Syrian refugees in Jordan who aim to eventually re-migrate to Europe or other non-regional countries are more likely to remain in Jordan, as their best chance for approval for third-country resettlement is while they are still in the country (KI5, KI6, KI8).

“If they [Syrian refugees] were wanting to migrate to Europe, their chances, although slim, were way better off in Jordan, not Syria, through third country resettlement programs.” – KI8

One expert observed that Syrian refugees in Jordan are well aware of the selection criteria used by INGOs for resettlement and understand that returning to Syria would jeopardize their eligibility (KI5). Despite ongoing repatriation efforts, experts widely agree that there is a significant likelihood that returnee refugees will re-migrate to Jordan or other non-regional countries, such as European states, if the situation in Syria continues to deteriorate. Several key informants (KI5, KI7) highlight that, in the absence of substantial improvements in security, economic conditions, and basic services, many refugees are likely to seek safer, more stable options for resettlement, particularly given the challenges of reintegration into a post-conflict Syria.

“Of course, they would migrate again, whether back to Jordan or anywhere else. Why would they stay in Syria if they felt unsafe and meeting basic needs was impossible there? If European countries are concerned about remigration directed at them, then it’s important to work on ensuring that returnees can live a dignified life, with access to employment, housing, healthcare, education, and other services and basic needs, in a safe and stable Syria. Without these basic human rights, no one in their right minds would stay in Syria – and no one should force them to stay.” – KI5

Influence of Jordan’s governance of refugee return to Syrian on the diplomacy of returns:

Just as regional mobility can impact diplomatic relations between Jordan and neighboring host countries, re-migration of Syrian refugees between Jordan and non-regional countries, such as European states, may also influence diplomatic ties. One interviewed expert pointed out that countries enforcing forced refugee return policies, including the EU, may inadvertently increase the refugee influx into countries with more welcoming policies, like Jordan (KI8). Consequently, such policy decisions could strain diplomatic relations by placing additional pressures on receiving countries. European discussions and policies around forced refugee returns to Syria could have a significant impact on Jordan in a number of ways. While Jordan has long been a key host country for refugees, increasing pressure on return could lead to an influx of refugees back into Jordan, further stretching its resources, complicating diplomatic relations, and potentially undermining the country’s role as a responsible host nation. The balance between managing refugee populations, maintaining security, and ensuring international support will be critical for Jordan as it navigates the evolving dynamics of refugee return and resettlement.

“This is the same for the EU or any other country that enforces a forced refugee return policy - the refugees could just migrate to another country with political stances like Jordan’s, because there is nothing positive, compelling, or even safe about the situation in Syria as it is right now. Therefore, it is absolutely critical that any return policies of Syrian refugees are developed with all hosting countries at the table, so that no host country suffers the consequences of the policy decisions of another host country.” – KI8

5. GAPs in Policy Mapping and Return Infrastructure

When it comes to mapping laws and policies, this mapping does a good job of highlighting the various difficulties that refugees encounter upon returning to Syria. It's critical to understand how these challenges are related; for example, a lack of employment skills can worsen economic instability, making it more difficult for returnees to start over. The suggested policy solutions are essential and realistic. While resolving safety issues and reconstructing infrastructure are essential for guaranteeing returnees' well-being and reintegration, vocational training and microfinance programs can empower them and promote economic growth. Involving local communities and returnees in these initiatives is particularly crucial since their perspectives can help develop more practical and culturally appropriate solutions. All things considered, this all-encompassing strategy is essential for aiding in the refugees' reintegration and promoting Syria's long-term stability.

There are still a lot of holes in the current rules and processes, which makes it hard for refugees to safely and sustainably return to Syria. Closing these gaps requires a holistic approach that includes human rights protections, reintegration aid, and security. By developing thorough and well-coordinated policies, stakeholders may create an atmosphere that not only promotes return but also, over time, protects the safety and dignity of returned.

Policy Recommendations for Supporting the Voluntary Return and Reintegration of Syrian Refugees

1. Comprehensive Legal and Institutional Frameworks for Return

- **Recommendation:** Develop and implement comprehensive legal frameworks that address the multifaceted challenges faced by refugees upon their return to Syria.
¹²⁴These frameworks should include clear procedures for voluntary return, safety guarantees, and human rights protections.
- **Rationale:** Gaps in existing laws and procedures currently hinder the safe and sustainable return of refugees. A coordinated policy approach that incorporates security measures, reintegration support, and the protection of returnees' rights is essential to close these gaps and ensure that returns are managed in a way that is both safe and dignified¹²⁵.

2. Economic Empowerment through Vocational Training and Microfinance Initiatives

- **Recommendation:** Introduce vocational training programs and microfinance initiatives to equip returnees with job skills and economic opportunities. Support for entrepreneurship and self-employment will help returnees rebuild their livelihoods and contribute to local economic recovery.

¹²⁴ UN habitat (2022 February). "Analysis of Syrian urban role". Legal thematic paper. Available at: <https://arablandinitiative.glt.net/sites/default/files/2023-09/docs/analysis-of-syrian-urban-law.pdf> .(Accessed 25 September 2024).

¹²⁵ ENSCWA. (2019 December 23). "policy gap analysis". An Examination of the Policy-based Gaps Hindering Syrian Arab Republic's Peacebuilding Process. Available at: https://www.unescwa.org/sites/default/files/pubs/pdf/policy_gap_analysis.pdf .(Accessed 25September 2024).

- **Rationale:** A lack of job skills and economic instability are key barriers to reintegration. By providing returnees with the tools to support themselves, these initiatives can help mitigate economic hardships and promote long-term stability for both returnees and host communities.¹²⁶
3. **Infrastructure Reconstruction and Service Delivery**
- **Recommendation:** Prioritize the rebuilding of critical infrastructure in returnees' home regions in Syria, focusing on essential services such as healthcare, education, and housing. This includes restoring damaged infrastructure and ensuring the availability of basic services to support returnees' reintegration.
 - **Rationale:** Returnees face significant challenges if they return to areas lacking basic infrastructure. Ensuring the availability of essential services is crucial for returnees to rebuild their lives and contribute to the country's recovery.
4. **Engagement of Local Communities in Reintegration Efforts**
- **Recommendation:** Involve both local communities and returnees in the planning and implementation of reintegration programs to ensure that these initiatives are culturally relevant and responsive to local needs.
 - **Rationale:** Engaging local communities and returnees in decision-making processes helps create more effective, inclusive, and sustainable solutions for reintegration. Their insights and feedback can guide policies that are better aligned with the realities on the ground.
5. **International Support and Funding for Repatriation Efforts**
- **Recommendation:** Ensure significant international support for repatriation efforts, particularly from institutions like the United Nations, through increased funding for reintegration programs, infrastructure development, and humanitarian aid.
 - **Rationale:** Successful repatriation requires adequate financial resources. International organizations and donor countries must provide sustained funding to support the safe return and reintegration of refugees, including resources for housing, healthcare, and education.
6. **Regional Cooperation and Collaboration**
- **Recommendation:** Strengthen regional cooperation between host countries such as Jordan and Turkey to improve the coordination and effectiveness of return programs. Collaborative efforts should focus on developing joint strategies for repatriation and reintegration, sharing resources, and enhancing logistical support.
 - **Rationale:** Regional cooperation can significantly enhance the effectiveness of repatriation processes. By working together, host countries can streamline return procedures, align policies, and ensure that refugees' rights and preferences are respected.

¹²⁶ UN habitat. (2022 July). "Recovery of Services and Infrastructure in Syria. "Not If, But How?". URF thematic paper. Available at: <https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2022/09/infrastructure.pdf> .(Accessed 25September 2024).

¹²⁶ OHCHR. "we didn't fear death but life there". Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/countries/syria/20240209-report-syrian-returnees.docx> (Accessed 25September 2024).

7. Enhancing International Cooperation and Support for Host Communities

- **Recommendation:** Increase international assistance to host countries to ensure that they can continue to provide support for both refugees and local communities. This should include investment in resilience-building programs and capacity development for host countries to manage the refugee crisis effectively.
- **Rationale:** Host countries, particularly those like Jordan, face immense pressure due to the high number of refugees. Strengthening international support for these countries will not only improve the lives of refugees but also contribute to regional stability. This support must prioritize both refugee needs and the well-being of host communities to ensure peaceful coexistence and sustainable development.

8. Human Rights and Protection Standards for Returnees

- **Recommendation:** Establish and enforce robust human rights protections for returnees to ensure that their return is voluntary, safe, and dignified. This includes protections against forced return, ensuring access to basic services, and addressing the risks of detention, violence, or persecution upon return.
- **Rationale:** The safety and dignity of returnees must be paramount. Clear protections should be put in place to ensure that returnees are not at risk of harm upon their return to Syria, including guarantees of safety from persecution, violence, or retribution.¹²⁷

9. Long-Term Monitoring and Support for Returnees

- **Recommendation:** Create mechanisms for the long-term monitoring of returnees to ensure their successful reintegration. This should include follow-up services to address ongoing needs related to employment, education, healthcare, and housing.
- **Rationale:** Reintegration is a long-term process that requires sustained support.¹²⁸ Monitoring mechanisms will help ensure that returnees continue to receive the assistance they need and that any emerging challenges are addressed in a timely manner.

6. Conclusion

The return migration governance between Jordan and Syria represents a complex and multifaceted issue, shaped by a confluence of social, economic, and political factors. Throughout this dossier, we have examined the various dimensions of return migration, highlighting the challenges and opportunities that exist in managing the return of Syrian refugees from Jordan to their homeland. One of the central themes that emerges from this study is the difficulty of achieving safe, voluntary, and sustainable returns under the current conditions in Syria. Despite some improvements in security in specific regions, the overall situation in Syria remains precarious, with ongoing conflicts, economic instability,

¹²⁷ UN (2022-2024). “strategic framework for the Syrian Arabic public”. Available at: <https://syria.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-10/UNSF%202022-2024%20English%20Final%20Signed.pdf> (Accessed 25 September 2024).

¹²⁸ ENSCWA. (2019 December 23).” policy gap analysis”. An Examination of the Policy-based Gaps Hindering Syrian Arab Republic’s Peacebuilding Process. Available at: https://www.unescwa.org/sites/default/files/pubs/pdf/policy_gap_analysis.pdf .(Accessed 25September 2024).

and human rights abuses posing significant risks to returnees. The Syrian government's reluctance to provide sufficient guarantees for the safety and protection of returnees further complicates the possibility of large-scale returns.

Jordan's role as a host country has been pivotal, as it continues to navigate the pressures of hosting a large refugee population while attempting to facilitate returns. The Jordanian government's diplomatic efforts, particularly through regional partnerships and negotiations with the Syrian regime, reflect its commitment to addressing the refugee crisis. However, these efforts are hampered by the lack of international support, dwindling humanitarian aid, and the challenges of balancing integration and return policies within Jordan. The involvement of international organizations such as UNHCR and IOM is crucial in providing logistical support and ensuring that returns are conducted in a manner that respects the dignity and rights of refugees. These organizations play a vital role in monitoring conditions, offering technical assistance, and advocating for policies that prioritize the safety and voluntariness of returns. Despite the significant diplomatic and logistical efforts made, the sustainability of return migration remains uncertain. Many returnees face the harsh reality of limited access to basic services, ongoing security threats, and a lack of economic opportunities upon their return to Syria. Consequently, some returnees may find themselves compelled to return to Jordan or seek refuge elsewhere, highlighting the cyclical nature of displacement and the challenges of achieving durable solutions.

Jordan and Syria's return migration administration is a fine balancing act that calls for strong policy frameworks, ongoing international cooperation, and a persistent dedication to ensuring the safety and rights of refugees. As this dossier has shown, achieving long-term and sustainable returns is difficult and calls for a thorough and well-coordinated strategy that tackles the underlying causes of displacement and facilitates returnees' long-term reintegration into Syrian society. The study's conclusions highlight the significance of continued efforts to guarantee that return migration is not only safe and voluntary but also supportive of the stability and well-being of those who decide to return in the long run.

7. References

- Al Arabiya Syria (2021). "The UNHCR in Jordan reveals the number of Syrians returning to their country since 2015." Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/Alarabiya.syria/posts/pfbid02aMS6VyddKcfrRPDdeUZz9zwVhYNkQszMZujLs5PUEVJnLLmNpRynqcmXoVjeNJTGI> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- Al Jazeera (2018). "Jordan reopens border with Syria after years of closure." Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/29/jordan-fully-reopens-main-crossing-with-syria> (Accessed 5 November 2024).
- Al Jazeera. (2018). "Jordan and Syria agree to reopen Naseeb border crossing." Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2018/10/14/jordan-and-syria-agree-to-reopen-naseeb-border-crossing> (Accessed 23 August 2024).
- Al Jazeera (2018). "Life returns to the Nasib border crossing between Jordan and Syria." Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.net/news/2018/10/14/life-returns-to-the-nasib-border-crossing> (Accessed 24 September 2024).
- Al Jazeera (2021). "Jordan, Syria Hold Talks to Restore Ties Amid Refugee Crisis." Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2016/6/23/syrian-refugees-stuck-on-jordan-border-have-nothing>.(Accessed 3 November 2024).
- Aljazeera (2021). "Jordan fully reopens main crossing with Syria." Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/29/jordan-fully-reopens-main-crossing-with-syria>(Accessed 29 November 2024).
- Al-Monitor (2022). "Erdogan unveils plans to send 1 million Syrians back amid anti-refugee Sentiment." Available at: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2022/05/erdogan-unveils-plans-send-1-million-syrians-back-anti-refugee-sentiment> (Accessed 27 August 2024).
- Al-Monitor (2022). "Erdogan unveils plans to send 1 million Syrians back amid anti-refugee sentiment." Available at: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2022/05/erdogan-unveils-plans-send-1-million-syrians-back-anti-refugee-sentiment> (Accessed 27 August 2024).
- Alqaralleh, Amir (2022). Jordan and Syrian humanitarian refugees' dilemma: international law perspective. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S240584402200665X>.(Accessed 3 November 2024)
- Amnesty International (2021). *Syria: Former refugees tortured, raped, disappeared after returning home*. Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2021/09/syria-former-refugees-tortured-raped-disappeared-after-returning-home/>(Accessed 21 August 2024).
- AP News (2023). "Lebanon and Syria: Refugee returns and challenges." Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/lebanon-syria-refugees-returns-ff41047896c7e16d0e5af0fae70d6c31>(Accessed 21 August 2024).

- AP News (2023). "Migrants and refugees in Syria and Lebanon: Safe zones and returns." Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/migrants-refugees-syria-eu-lebanon-safe-zones-returns-3b52a8b2d55acb6838c1e34916638f4b> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Awamleh, Zaid (2024). Hosting Syrian Refugees through the Development Lens: "The Case of Jordan." Available at: <https://journals.openedition.org/remi/25462>. (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- Bani Salameh, M. (2024). "Beyond Borders: Impacts of the Syrian Refugee Crisis on Jordan." Available at: <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/1185399> (Accessed 24 September 2024).
- BBC Arabic (2018). "Jordanian-Syrian agreement to reopen an important border crossing between the two Countries." Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/arabic/middleeast-45857150> (Accessed 24 September 2024).
- BBC News (2018). Middle East's share of world arms market "rising." Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-44198304> (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- Carnegie Endowment for International Peace (2015). *Jordan's refugee crisis*. Available at: <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2015/09/jordans-refugee-crisis?lang=en> (Accessed 31 August 2024).
- Chehayeb, K. (2022). Donors pledge \$6.4 billion for Syria at Brussels conference. Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/brussels-syria-donors-conference-bdbf13a6e6aaeb81b53274cb89ddac26> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Council on Foreign Relations (2022). *U.S. and international policy to protect refugees: A timeline*. Available at: <https://www.cfr.org/blog/us-and-international-policy-protect-refugees-timeline> (Accessed 31 August 2024).
- Culbertson, S. & Kumar, K. Rand Corporation (2019). *Jobs can improve the lives of Syrian refugees and their hosts*. Available at: <https://www.rand.org/pubs/commentary/2019/03/jobs-can-improve-the-lives-of-syrian-refugees-and-their.html> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- Debre, I. (2023). *Jordan's efforts to return Syrian refugees face challenges*. Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/jordan-syria-refugees-civil-war-return-4a87a2f77db9e6099306db7554898062> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Dhingra (2023). "Syrian refugees face a grim future without international policy shifts." Available at: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/syrian-refugees-face-a-grim-future-without-international-policy-shifts/> (Accessed 23 September 2024).
- Doosje, B. et al. (2022). Mental health and psychosocial support for Syrian refugees in Jordan: A qualitative study. Available at: <https://bmcpyschology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40359-022-00963-w> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- EEAS (2024). "The EU and the crisis in Syria." Available at: https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/eu-and-crisis-syria-o_en. (Accessed 2 November 2024)

- ENSCWA (2019).” policy gap analysis.” An Examination of the Policy-based Gaps Hindering Syrian Arab Republic’s Peacebuilding Process. Available at: https://www.unescwa.org/sites/default/files/pubs/pdf/policy_gap_analysis.pdf.(Accessed 25 September 2024).
- ENSCWA (2019).” policy gap analysis.” An Examination of the Policy-based Gaps Hindering Syrian Arab Republic’s Peacebuilding Process. Available at: https://www.unescwa.org/sites/default/files/pubs/pdf/policy_gap_analysis.pdf.(Accessed 25 September 2024).
- EU Global Strategy (2020). “A Secure Europe in a Better World.” Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/documents-publications/publications/european-security-strategy-secure-europe-better-world/>.(Accessed 3 November 2024).
- European Commission (2022). *Annual Report on Migration and Asylum*. Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-07/00_eu_arm2022_report.pdf (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- European External Action Service (2023). “*The European Union and Jordan*.” Available at: https://www.eeas.europa.eu/jordan/european-union-and-jordan_en?s=201(Accessed 31 August 2024).
- Financial Times (2018). “Jordan and Syria agree to reopen Naseeb border crossing.” Available at: <https://www.ft.com/content/e580c1a6-d6de-11e8-aa22-36538487e3do>(Accessed 21 August 2024).
- France 24 (2018). “Nearly 30,000 Syrians return home from Jordan after border reopens.” Available at: <https://www.france24.com/en/20181203-nearly-30000-syrians-return-home-jordan-after-border-reopens> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- France 24 (2021). “Syrian refugees tortured, raped, and missing after returning home, Amnesty says.” Available at: <https://www.france24.com/en/middle-east/20210907-syrian-refugees-tortured-raped-and-missing-after-returning-home-amnesty-says>(Accessed 23 August 2024).
- Francis, A. (2015). Jordan’s Refugee Crisis. Available at: <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2015/09/jordans-refugee-crisis?lang=en> (Accessed 24 September 2024)
- Frelick, B. Human Rights Watch. (2023). “*No, Syria is still not safe for refugee returns*.” Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/09/29/no-syria-still-not-safe-refugee-returns> (Accessed 31 August 2024).
- Gordon, J. (2021). *The impact of the Syrian refugee crisis on Jordan’s economy*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43508-021-00019-6> (Accessed 23 August 2024).
- Heydemann, S. (2024). Syria normalization: The failure of defensive diplomacy. Available at: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/syria-normalization-the-failure-of-defensive-diplomacy/> (Accessed 27 August 2024).
- Human Rights Watch (2017). “I have no idea why they sent us back.” Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2017/10/02/i-have-no-idea-why-they-sent-us-back/jordanian-deportations-and-expulsions-syrian>. (Accessed 29 November 2024).

- Human Rights Watch (2018). "Syria: Questions and Answers on New Property Law." Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2018/05/29/syria-questions-and-answers-new-property-law>.(Accessed 29 November 2024).
- Human Rights Watch (2024). Syria events in 2023. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/syria>(Accessed 29 November 2024).
- Human Rights Watch (2024): "Jordan: No Jobs, No Future: Refugees and Work in Jordan." Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/jordan> (Accessed 5 November 2024).
- Human Rights Watch (2021). "Our lives are like death": Syrian refugee returns from Lebanon and Jordan. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2021/10/20/our-lives-are-death/syrian-refugee-returns-lebanon-and-jordan> (Accessed 23 September 2024).
- International Center for Migration Policy Development (2019). "Integrated Border Management in Jordan." Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/integrated-border-management-in-jordan-ibm-jordan> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- International Law and Policy Brief (2022). "*International obligations of asylum countries to protect refugees.*" Available at: <https://studentbriefs.law.gwu.edu/ilpb/2022/04/29/international-obligations-of-asylum-countries-to-protect-refugees/> (Accessed 31 August 2024).
- International Rescue Committee IRC (2023). "Syrian refugees highlight worsening living conditions in the region, and fewer than 2% envisage returning home." Available at: <https://www.rescue.org/press-release/syrian-refugees-highlight-worsening-living-conditions-region-and-fewer-2-envisage> (Accessed 23 August 2024).
- International Organization For Migration (2021)." Study Research On Vulnerability To Trafficking In Persons Among The Crisis-Affected Populations In The Levant Region." Available at:https://jordan.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbdl991/files/documents/jo_country-trends_o.pdf. (Accessed 29 November 2024).
- Inter Sector Working Group (2024). "Refugee Response & Resilience Strategy." Available at: <https://jordanrefugeeshub.unhcr.org/DOCs/ISWG%20Jordan%20Refugee%20Response%202024-25%20Strategy.pdf> (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- Istaiteyeh, Rasha (2023). *Charting the path home: Syrian refugee return from Jordan to Syria.* Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/charting-the-path-home-syrian-refugee-return-from-jordan-to-syria>(Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Jordan Times (2024)." Safadi, EU's Schinas discuss partnerships, refugee support." Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/safadi-eus-schinas-discuss-partnerships-refugee-support> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- Jordan Times (2024). "Foreign minister calls for increased support for Syrian refugees." Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/foreign-minister-calls-increased-support-syrian-refugees> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

- Jordan Times (2024). “Syrian refugees will not be resettled in Jordan – interior minister” Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/syrian-refugees-will-not-be-resettled-jordan-%E2%80%94-interior-minister> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- Jordan Times. (2023). “Jordan calls for global fund for voluntary, safe return of Syrian refugees” Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/jordan-calls-global-fund-voluntary-safe-return-syrian-refugees> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- Jordan’s Response to the Syria Crisis (2023): “Update.” Available at: <http://www.jrp.gov.jo/> (Accessed 5 November 2024).
- Jordan’s Refugee Policy and Deportation Laws (2015). “Refugee Law and Policy: Jordan.” Available at: <https://maint.loc.gov/law/help/refugee-law/jordan.php> (Accessed 29 November 2024).
- JT. Namasis (2020). Overwhelming majority of Jordanians continue to empathize with refugees – UNHCR study. Available at: <https://www.namasis.com/media-coverage/overwhelming-majority-of-jordanians-continue-to-empathise-with-refugees-unhcr-study/> (Accessed 25 September 2024)
- Juline Beaujouan and Amjed Rasheed (2022), “*The Syrian Refugee Crisis in Jordan And Lebanon: Impact And Implications.*” Available at: <https://peacerep.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/MEPOPaper-JBAR-002.pdf>. (Accessed 23 September 2024).
- Jusoor. (2018). Nassib border crossing: Impact of its closure and reopening on Syria and the region. Available at: <https://jusoor.co/en/details/nassib-border-crossing> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- Kassous, S. (2023). Syrian refugees: Why are host countries now focusing on the issue of voluntary return? Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/arabic/65731848> (Accessed 24 September 2024).
- Kassous, S. BBC News Arabic. (2024). The Syrian refugee crisis: Between hope of return and challenges of integration. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/arabic/articles/cy918kdg1jjo> (Accessed 24 September 2024).
- Marks, J. (2021). By land or by sea: Syrian refugees weigh their futures. Available at: <https://www.refugeesinternational.org/reports-briefs/by-land-or-by-sea-syrian-refugees-weigh-their-futures/> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Middle East Eye (2023) Syria’s return to the Arab diplomatic fold is not a top concern for Biden. Available at: <https://www.middleeasteye.net/opinion/syria-us-reintegration-arab-diplomatic-fold-biden-concern> (Accessed 29 November 2024).
- Middle East Eye. (2023). “Jordan’s plan for Syria normalisation: Refugees, drugs and militias.” Available at: <https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/jordan-syria-plan-normalisation-refugees-drugs-militias> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- Middle East Institute. (2020). “Gulf States and the Future of Syria’s Reconstruction.” Available at: <https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/policy-analysis/syrias-normalization-and-gcc-adjusting-new-modus-vivendi> (Accessed 5 November).

- Muiderman, Karlijn. (2015). The Migration Trail – European migration policies in a globalizing world. Available at: <https://www.thebrokeronline.eu/article/the-migration-trail-d94/> (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- Norwegian Refugee Council. (2015). Thousands of refugees return to Syria from Jordan. Available at: <https://www.nrc.no/news/2015/october/thousands-of-refugees-return-to-syria-from-jordan/> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- Norwegian Refugee Council. (2019). *Legal identity and housing, land, and property rights of Syrian refugees from a durable solutions perspective*. Available at: <https://www.nrc.no/globalassets/pdf/reports/legal-identity-and-hlp-rights-of-syrian-refugees/legal-identity-and-hlp-rights-of-syrian-refugees-from-a-durable-solutions-perspective---english.pdf> (Accessed 31 August 2024).
- Obeidat, R. Middle East Institute. (2021). *Border opportunities: Reviving the Jordan-Syria free trade zone*. Available at: <https://www.mei.edu/publications/border-opportunities-reviving-jordan-syria-free-trade-zone> (Accessed 31 August 2024).
- OHCHR (2024). “We didn’t fear death but life there.” Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/countries/syria/20240209-report-syrian-returnees.docx> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- RT Arabic. (2023). “In 6 months... the United Nations reveals the number of Syrian refugees who returned from Jordan to their homeland.” Available at: <https://arabic.rt.com/middle-east/1585132-> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- Syrian Network for Human Rights. (2022). At least 196 arbitrary arrests/detentions documented in Syria in November 2022, including 11 children and three women, mostly at the hands of Syrian regime forces. Available at: <https://snhr.org/blog/2022/12/02/at-least-196-arbitrary-arrests-detentions-documented-in-syria-in-november-2022-including-11-children-and-three-women-mostly-at-the-hands-of-syrian-regime-forces/> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Syrian Network for Human Rights. (2023). “At least 2,221 arbitrary arrests/detentions documented in Syria in 2022, including 148 children and 457 women (adult female), with 213 cases documented in December.” Available at: <https://snhr.org/blog/2023/01/03/at-least-2221-arbitrary-arrests-detentions-documented-in-syria-in-2022-including-148-children-and-457-women-adult-female-with-213-cases-documented-in-december/> (Accessed 22 September 2024).
- The Guardian. (2023). “Jordan Pushes for International Aid to Rebuild Syria and Support Refugee.” Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/feb/10/pressure-mounts-on-un-to-provide-urgent-support-to-north-western-syria> (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- The Jordan Times JT. (2023). “2,582 Syrian refugees left Jordan during first 7 months of 2023 UNHCR.” Available at: <https://www.jordantimes.com/news/local/2582-syrian-refugees-left-jordan-during-first-7-months-2023-%E2%80%94-unhcr> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- The Jordan Times. (2021). “Jordan’s refugee burden: A review of the facts. Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/unhcr-reveals-rising-refugee-poverty-amidst-jordans-economic-challenges> (Accessed 5 November 2024).

- The Jordan Times. (2021). "Jordan's refugee burden: A review of the facts." Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/unhcr-reveals-rising-refugee-poverty-amidst-jordans-economic-challenges> (Accessed 5 November 2024).
- The Jordan Times. (2023). 2,582 Syrian refugees left Jordan during first 7 months of 2023 UNHCR. Available at: <https://jordantimes.com/news/local/2582-syrian-refugees-left-jordan-during-first-7-months-2023-%E2%80%94-unhcr> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- The National. (2022). "Jordan–Syria Security Cooperation: A New Phase in Regional Diplomacy." Available at: https://www.3rpsyriacrisis.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/RSO_2024_full_publication.pdf (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- The New Arab Staff, T NAS (2021). Jordan to reopen Syria border crossing at full capacity. Available at: <https://www.newarab.com/news/jordan-reopen-syria-border-crossing-full-capacity> (Accessed 23 August 2024).
- The World Bank in Jordan (2024). "The World Bank is working for the people of Jordan to create more and better opportunities for all." Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/jordan/overview> (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- UK Home Office (2022). "Country Policy and Information Note: Security Situation, Syria." Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/syria-country-policy-and-information-notes/country-policy-and-information-note-security-situation-syria-june-2022-accessible> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- UN Habitat (2022). "Analysis of Syrian urban role." Available at: <https://arablandinitiative.gltm.net/sites/default/files/2023-09/docs/analysis-of-syrian-urban-law.pdf> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- UN habitat (2022). "Recovery of Services and Infrastructure in Syria." Available at: <https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2022/09/infrastructure.pdf> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- UN Treaties (2024). "International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights" Available at: https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=IV-4&chapter=4&clang=en (Accessed 25 August 2024).
- UNHCR (2019) "UNHCR continues to support refugees in Jordan through 2019." Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/jo/12449-unhcr-continues-to-support-refugees-in-jordan-throughout-2019.html> (Accessed 25 September 2024).
- UNHCR (2023). "Syria situation 2023–2024" Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/situations/syria-situation> (Accessed 29 November 2024).
- UNHCR (2024), "Syrian Refugee Return: Policy and Perspectives." Available at: https://www.3rpsyriacrisis.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Intention_Survey_RPIS_2024.pdf (Accessed 29 November 2024).

- UNHCR (2018)., “*The Legal Framework of the Syrian Crisis and Refugees: The Impact of Law No. 10 on the Right to Return.*” Available at: [UNHCR Report. https://www.unhcr.org/lb/wp-content/uploads/sites/16/2018/06/AUB-IFI-101-fact-Sheet-2018-English.pdf](https://www.unhcr.org/lb/wp-content/uploads/sites/16/2018/06/AUB-IFI-101-fact-Sheet-2018-English.pdf).
- UNHCR (2022). “Jordan: Zaatari Refugee Camp.” Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/jo/wp-content/uploads/sites/60/2022/02/1-Zaatari-Fact-Sheet-January-2022-final.pdf> (Accessed 3 November 2024).
- UNHCR –Data Portal (2024). “Syria Regional Refugee Response: Durable Solutions” Available at: https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria_durable_solutions (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- UNHCR (2023). “Vulnerability Assessment Framework (VAF) – Jordan.” Available At: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/working-group/54> (Accessed 5 November 2024).
- UNHCR (2020). “UNHCR’s Monitoring of Refugee Returns to Syria.” Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria> (Accessed 5 November 2024).
- UNHCR (2024). Syria Regional Refugee Response: Durable solutions. Available at: https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria_durable_solutions(Accessed 21 August 2024).
- UNHCR (2022). “Eleven years on, mounting challenges push many displaced Syrians to the brink.” Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/news/briefing-notes/eleven-years-mounting-challenges-push-many-displaced-syrians-brink>.
- UNHCR (2022). Eleven years on, mounting challenges push many displaced Syrians to the brink. Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/news/briefing-notes/eleven-years-mounting-challenges-push-many-displaced-syrians-brink> (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- UNHCR Jordan. (2020). “Voluntary Return from Jordan to Syria.” Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria/location/36>.(Accessed 5 November 2024).
- United Nations (2024). “*Syria facing highest levels of humanitarian need since start of 13-year crisis.*” Available at: <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15744.doc.htm> (Accessed 20 August 2024).
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2021). *Syria situation: Global report 2021*. Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/syria-situation-global-report-2021>(Accessed 21 August 2024).
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2023). *Jordan country operation update: August 2023*. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/106139> (Accessed 30 August 2024).
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2019). Jordan: How the Global Compact on Refugees is turning into action in Jordan. Available at: <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/gcr-action/countries/jordan> (Accessed 24 September 2024).
- United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner (2024) Syrian returnees subjected to gross human rights violations and abuses – UN report. Available at:

<https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2024/02/syrian-returnees-subjected-gross-human-rights-violations-and-abuses-un> (Accessed 23 September 2024).

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2024). *Syrian Arab Republic: 2024 Humanitarian Needs Overview*. Available at <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/syrian-arab-republic/syrian-arab-republic-2024-humanitarian-needs-overview-february-2024> (Accessed 20 August 2024).

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2023). “*Syrian Arab Republic: Humanitarian access severity overview (June 2023)*”. Available at: <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/syrian-arab-republic/syrian-arab-republic-humanitarian-access-severity-overview-june-2023> (Accessed 23 August 2024).

United Nations Volunteers (2018). *Facilitating social cohesion between Syrian refugees and host communities in Jordan*. Available at: <https://www.unv.org/Success-stories/facilitating-social-cohesion-between-syrian-refugees-and-host-communities-jordan> (Accessed 21 August 2024).

World Bank Group (2024). “Jordan: Improving Economic Opportunities for Syrian Refugees and Host Communities.” Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2024/11/06/jordan-improving-economic-opportunities-for-syrian-refugees-and-host-communities>. (Accessed 29 November 2024).

World Bank (2019). “*The mobility of displaced Syrians: An economic and social analysis.*” Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/jordan/publication/jordan-economic-monitor-fall-2021> (Accessed 3 November 2024).

Zaid Awalmeh (2024). “Hosting Syrian Refugees through the Development Lens”: The Case of Jordan” Available at: <https://journals.openedition.org/remi/25462> (Accessed 25 August 2024).

Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek and Fatma Yılmaz-Elmas (2024): Refugee governance in the Middle East: insights from Turkey, Lebanon and Jordan In: *Research Handbook on Asylum and Refugee Policy*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781802204599.00018>.

Annex 1: List of Interviewed Organizations

Nr.	Organization Name
1.	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)
2.	CARE International in Jordan
3.	The International Organization for Migration (IOM)
4.	Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC)
5.	International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD)
6.	Syrian Refugee Affairs Directorate (SRAD)

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